

D5.2 Report on initial use case evaluation

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List of acronyms and terms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AV	Autonomous Vehicle
BEV	Bird's Eye View
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
CFS	Completely Fair Scheduler
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CLIP	Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining
CMT	Cross-Modal-Detector
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DE	Deep Ensemble
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
GPS	Global Positioning System
HuIL	Human-in-the-Loop
HW	Hardware
IoU	Intersection Over Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LKS	Lane Keeping System
LLMCD	Last Layer Monte-Carlo-Dropout
mAP	Mean Average Precision
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MPC	Model-Predictive-Controller
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OSI	Open Simulation Interface
PBOD	Pillar-Based Object Detection
ROS	Robot Operating System
ROTR	Rule Of The Road

RSI	Road Side Infrastructure
RTA	Runtime Assurance
SAFEOD	Situational Awareness Feature Enhanced Object Detection
SLS	Semantic Labelling System
SML	Second Moment Regression Loss
SW	Software
TM	Traffic Management
TN	True Negative
TP	True Positive
UC	Use Case
UQ	Uncertainty Quantification
VIL	Vehicle in the Loop
ViT	Vision Transformer
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WCET	Worst-case Execution Time
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
XiL	X-in-the-Loop
YOLO	You Only Look Once

1. Introduction

1.1. Althena concept and approach

Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions have emerged thanks to novel Artificial Intelligence (AI) which can be trained with huge amounts of data to produce driving functions with better-than-human performance under certain conditions. The race on AI continues building hardware (HW) and software (SW) frameworks to manage and process even larger real and synthetic datasets to train increasingly accurate AI models. However, AI remains largely unexplored with respect to explainability (interpretability of model functioning), privacy preservation (exposure of sensitive data), ethics (bias and wanted/unwanted behaviour), and accountability (responsibilities of AI outputs). These features will establish the basis of trustworthy AI, as a novel paradigm to fully understand and trust AI in operation, while using it at its full capabilities for the benefit of society. Althena will contribute to build Explainable AI (XAI) in CCAM development and testing frameworks, researching three main AI pillars: data (real/synthetic data management), models (data fusion, hybrid AI approaches), and testing (physical/virtual X- in the loop (XiL) set-ups with scalable Machine Learning Operations (MLOps)). A human-centric methodology will be created to derive trustworthy AI dimensions from user-identified group needs in CCAM applications. Althena will innovate proposing a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) on XAI and an analysis to explore trade-offs between these dimensions. Demonstrators will show the Althena methodology in four critical use cases: perception (what does the AI perceive and why), situational awareness (what is the AI understanding about the current driving environment, including the driver state), decision (why a certain decision is taken), and traffic management (how transport-level applications interoperate with AI-enabled systems operating at vehicle level). Created data and tools will be made available via European data sharing initiatives (OpenData and OpenTools) to foster research on trustworthy AI for CCAM.

1.2. Purpose of this deliverable

This deliverable is the second report of work package 5 (“Deploy & Test”) and is related to the tasks 5.2 to 5.5. Each of these tasks is dedicated to one of the four use cases in Althena.

- UC-1: Trustworthy Perception Systems for CCAM
- UC-2: AI extended Situational Awareness/Understanding
- UC-3: Trustworthy and Human understandable decision-making
- UC-4: AI-based Traffic Management

This deliverable will cover the initial demonstrator validation and evaluation for the first cycle of the project. Due to the early stage of the project, the activities and results so far are mainly limited to simulations and the evaluation of the individual subsystems. The validation and evaluation of the overall systems will take place in the second half of the project and will then be reported in deliverable 5.3.

This report focuses more on the results, while the algorithms are explained in more details in deliverable 3.2.

1.3. Structure of this deliverable

This deliverable is structured according to the demonstrators since it is a joint report of the tasks 5.2 to 5.5. Each of the five main chapters is dedicated to one demonstrator. First the setup of the demonstrator is explained, followed by the activities and evaluation results of the 1st project cycle. Finally, each demonstrator gives an outlook of the plans for the 2nd project cycle.

- Chapter 2 is related to Task 5.2 “UC-1: Trustworthy Perception Systems for CCAM” and its demonstrator “Reliable Pedestrian Detection in Urban Environments”.
- Chapter 3 is related to Task 5.3 “UC-2: AI extended Situational Awareness/Understanding” and its first demonstrator “Collision prediction with Hybrid AI data fusion models”.
- Chapter 4 is related to Task 5.3 “UC-2: AI extended Situational Awareness/Understanding” and its second demonstrator “Robust Prediction modules for Robo-taxis in urban environments”.
- Chapter 5 is related to Task 5.4 “UC-3: Trustworthy and Human understandable Decision-making” and its demonstrator “Explainable and robust decision making (manoeuvre and trajectory)”.
- Chapter 6 is related to Task 5.5 “UC-4: AI-based Traffic management” and its demonstrator “AI Models and Traffic Management”.

2. UC1 - Trustworthy Perception Systems for CCAM

2.1. Setup (IKA)

2.1.1. Offline Demonstrator

In the first UC demonstration, an *offline* demonstrator is being showcased (see Figure 1). The demonstration is based on recorded data from a demonstrator vehicle, simulated data and based on existing publicly available datasets on perception. This allows for faster prototyping, testing, and evaluation of different approaches developed within the Althena project. UC1 demonstrates a composition of several methodologies, mechanisms and documentation principles that are designed to enhance a blackbox AI detection function with a specific focus on pedestrian detection in urban scenarios.

Figure 1: 1st Althena Cycle - "Offline" UC1 Demonstrator - Components

2.2. Results of the evaluation in the 1st cycle (IKA)

2.2.1. Explainable Layers

IKA proposed a saliency map generation approach for a multi-camera detection model, aiming to enhance the understanding of the detectors model's behaviour and provide insights into which regions of input images are most influential in determining object detection predictions [1]. The simple and effective method generates saliency maps during runtime which indicate where the model is putting its attention on, as shown Figure 2.

A quantitative evaluation tested the quality produced by the method using positive and negative perturbation tests where certain parts of the six input camera images are masked (red) to measure the effectiveness of each approach. An example for a negative perturbation is shown in Figure 2 (top right). The result of the positive perturbation test is shown in Figure 3 and proves the reliability and accuracy of the method regarding a deployment in the UC1 demonstrator. The approach outperforms existing real-time saliency generation methods but is limited to a specific architecture paradigm.

Figure 2: Explainable layer visualization for a camera-based 3D object detector.

Figure 3: Quality assessment for different mechanisms. Lower AUC is better.

In the 1st Aithena cycle this method is demonstrated on the nuScenes dataset and for the SpatialDETR [2] architecture for prototyping and evaluation. For 2nd Aithena cycle it is aimed to bring this mechanism into a real-world demonstrator. The output of this mechanism is then transmitted to the XAI interface that can be consumed by different entities. A prototype for the XAI interface is shown in section 2.2.4

2.2.2. Robust Multi-Modal Pedestrian Detection

For autonomous vehicles to gain widespread acceptance and trust, they must demonstrate robustness, reliability and accuracy under adverse weather and road conditions. A consistent and open-source evaluation framework for assessing the robustness of multi-modal detection algorithms has been developed by IKA. The evaluation dataset and framework-named MultiCorrupt [3] - consist of ten multi-modal sensor corruptions that affect both camera and LiDAR data. Each corruption is implemented in three severity levels where level 1 reflects the lightest severity and level 3 the strongest corruption on the sensor modalities. The benchmark includes the following corruptions:

Points Reducing: Randomly drops points from the point cloud, with the fraction of removed points increasing with the severity level.

Temporal Misalignment: Applies temporal misalignment to camera and point cloud data to simulate imperfect synchronization between different modalities.

Spatial Misalignment: Introduces both translation and rotation misalignment between the point cloud and camera inputs, varying the angle of rotation and proportion of affected data

depending on the severity level.

Motion Blur: Incorporates jitter noise into the data to replicate motion, vibrations, and the rolling shutter effect.

Missing Camera: Randomly drops frames from multiple cameras at each timestamp to simulate frame loss.

Beams Reducing: Reduces the number of LiDAR beams with increasing severity levels.

Fog: Simulates fog in point clouds using a method that translates the parameters of LiDAR fog generation into an image fog generation method.

Snow: Uses an approach that samples snow particles and models them as opaque spheres, and models the reflection properties of wet ground surfaces. Corrupts point cloud and image data corresponding to defined levels of snowfall.

Darkness: Simulates low light conditions with Poisson Gaussian noise.

Brightness: Introduces overexposure by adding brightness in the HSV space of the images.

Consequently, five top-performing state-of-the-art 3D object detectors have been evaluated on MultiCorrupt. These models belong to the best performing detectors on the nuScenes dataset. The results of the benchmark are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Model	Beams Red.	Brightness	Darkness	Fog	Missing Cam.	Motion Blur	Points Red.	Snow	Spatial Mis.	Temporal Mis.	mRA
CMT [1]	0.786	0.937	0.948	0.806	0.974	0.841	0.925	0.833	0.809	0.788	0.865
DeepInteraction [5]	0.655	0.969	0.929	0.583	0.842	0.832	0.882	0.759	0.731	0.768	0.795
TransFusion [4]	0.633	0.993	0.988	0.754	0.985	0.826	0.851	0.748	0.685	0.777	0.824
SparseFusion [2]	0.689	0.975	0.963	0.767	0.954	0.848	0.879	0.770	0.714	0.777	0.834
BEVfusion [3]	0.676	0.967	0.969	0.752	0.974	0.866	0.872	0.774	0.705	0.742	0.830

Figure 4: Robustness evaluation of top-performing object detectors against several types of corruptions. Higher score is better.

Figure 5: Detailed robustness evaluation of object detectors. Higher score is better.

The findings indicate that existing multi-modal 3D object detection algorithms generally exhibit different robustness behaviour depending on their specific fusion, alignment, and training strategies. These investigations helped us to select the most robust and best performing multi-modal detectors for future developments in the Athena project. CMT (Cross-Modal-Detector) [4] as proven to be the detector with the highest accuracy and robustness scores, as shown in Figure 6.

Model	Inference Time ↑	NDS Score ↑	mAP (%) ↑	mRA (%) ↑	mRRA (%) ↑
CMT	15 FPS	72.90	70.28	0.865	7.161
DeepInteraction	3 FPS	69.09	68.72	0.795	-7.221
TransFusion	6.5 FPS	70.84	66.72	0.824	-1.718
SparseFusion	10 FPS	73.15	71.20	0.834	3.033
BEVfusion	6.5 FPS	71.44	68.72	0.742	Baseline Model

Figure 6: Performance overview of multi-modal object 3D object detectors.

Furthermore, the architecture’s inference time is suitable for real-time object detection using an Nvidia GTX 4090 in our prototype vehicle. Detailed metrics for the individual classes in nuScenes for the CMT model are further reported in Figure 7.

Object Class	Average Precision ↑	Average Translation Error ↓	Average Scale Error ↓	Average Orientation Error ↓	Average Velocity Error ↓	Average Attribute Error ↓
car	0.872	0.174	0.142	0.049	0.271	0.189
truck	0.623	0.341	0.175	0.058	0.247	0.195
bus	0.743	0.353	0.166	0.089	0.448	0.229
trailer	0.409	0.535	0.215	0.416	0.209	0.159
construction_vehicle	0.248	0.748	0.455	0.799	0.113	0.323
pedestrian	0.865	0.153	0.284	0.304	0.200	0.092
motorcycle	0.737	0.227	0.245	0.218	0.392	0.221
bicycle	0.639	0.183	0.258	0.523	0.198	0.008
traffic_cone	0.780	0.152	0.314	N/A	N/A	N/A
barrier	0.713	0.236	0.261	0.044	N/A	N/A

Figure 7: Detailed detection metrics for CMT.

The model achieved an Average Precision of **0.865 for the class pedestrian** which is one of the highest values for the nuScenes detection benchmark. If pedestrians in proximity of the ego vehicle are benchmarked (distance < 15) the **average precision increases up to 97%**.

Consequently, future developments in UC1 regarding robust and reliable pedestrian detection will focus on CMT [4] or on an CMT-like architecture approach. That includes the integration of explainable layers and uncertainty quantification and the connection to the XAI-interface.

2.2.3. Model Uncertainty Estimation

Uncertainty quantification (UQ) is an essential aspect of perception systems, as it provides valuable information about the reliability and confidence of the detected objects. Understanding the uncertainty associated within the perception pipeline allows autonomous vehicles to make more informed decisions, especially in safety-critical scenarios. The IKA UC1 demonstrator includes an uncertainty estimation for its perception models allowing additional feedback to the user about the perception system and allowing downstream tasks to perform more informed decisions. For example, if the perception model is uncertain about a current situation due to

adverse weather conditions or sensor blockage, the uncertainty will increase. Consequently, the user could be informed that the perception system currently reaches its limitations, and the trajectory planning could use this information to drive more passively.

Building on these considerations, IKA proposes Last Layer Monte-Carlo-Dropout (LLMCD) as an efficient real-time capable way to estimate uncertainties in a detector model. LLMCD results in pivotal modifications to the original PBOD [5] model. Last Layer refers to the regression head phase, that is modified. During inference the forward pass of the regression head is done in parallel with activated dropout layers. Then, the outputs of these sub ensembles are merged again and the variance of the predictions are used as an uncertainty measure. Additionally, the Second-Moment Regression Loss (SML) was implemented, which tackles the underestimation of uncertainty in Monte-Carlo-Dropout approaches.

For the evaluation of the proposed approach, the nuScenes dataset is used for training and testing. In each experiment, the same training and test set is used to ensure that the results are comparable. For all training runs with LLMCD, $n = 20$ detection heads with a dropout rate of $p = 0.2$ are used.

Model	AP cars@0.5	Model	NLL cars@0.5
Vanilla PBOD	0.6559	Vanilla PBOD	n.a.
PBOD + LLMCD	0.5389	PBOD + LLMCD	-3.17
PBOD + LLMCD + SML $\beta = 0.5$	0.5046	PBOD + LLMCD + SML $\beta = 0.5$	-3.51
PBOD + LLMCD + SML $\beta = 0.75$	0.2966	PBOD + LLMCD + SML $\beta = 0.75$	-3.42
Ensemble n=5	0.6078	Ensemble n=5	18.7
Ensemble n=10	0.607	Ensemble n=10	-3.18

Figure 8: Detection accuracy and NLL uncertainty score for the different model variants.

Model	Inference Time
Vanilla PBOD	30ms
PBOD + LLMCD	40ms
Ensemble n=5	100ms
Ensemble n=10	200ms

Figure 9: Inference speed comparison of the different model variants.

The vanilla PBOD [5] model achieves the best performance of all models, setting a benchmark for the other models. The introduction of the LLMCD approach leads to a deterioration in the detection performance. By using the SML with $\beta = 0.5$, the performance has only decreased minimally but achieves the best UQ estimate.

The proposed method, Last Layer Monte Carlo Dropout (LLMCD), is a real-time capable method that achieves both decent detection performance and good results for UQ. The results are comparable to those of the deep ensemble (DE), but LLMCD is 5 times faster. However, the precision of the LLMCD network is lower than the precision of the vanilla network and of the DE.

In future work, IKA wants to improve UQ for query-based object detectors (such as CMT and SpatialDETR) which have a much-simplified detection pipeline allowing an easier integration into the UC1 demonstrator. It is also believed that the query-based approach won't suffer that much from a performance drop using the LLMCD approach. IKA further aims to integrate the uncertainty measure into the XAI interface as additional information for the user in the final UC1 demonstration.

2.2.4. XAI-Interface Prototype

A XAI-interface is necessary to build a bridge between the enriched AI model and the user. IKA implemented an interactive prototype XAI-interface that aimed to visualize the inner state of a detection model. The current version of the interface is implemented in Python for offline demonstration with the nuScenes dataset.

Currently, for the 1st Athena cycle, the attention maps (saliency maps) and the sensor usage for multi-view cameras can be displayed with the XAI interface, as shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11. In future iterations the interface will be extended to visualize model uncertainty and a multi-modal sensor usage display including the LiDAR usage. Furthermore, the interface should be implemented in ROS RVIZ which would allow a real-time usage in the demonstrator.

Figure 10: XAI-Interface Prototype for explainable model layers.

Figure 11: XAI-Interface Prototype which displays the sensor usage of a detection model with multiple sensor inputs. Green bar on top indicates the sensor usage for a specific detection.

2.2.5. Model & Datacards

Model and data cards are comprehensive documents that contain essential information to accompany a trained machine learning model. The goal is to provide a standardized documentation procedure that will communicate not only the performance evaluation of the model but extend it with model development and usage information.

Within the Athena project, a model card template was proposed in WP3. This template includes all necessary information principles and is adapted and improved compared to existing model card templates in the literature. To further increase the transparency and explainability of the used models in UC 1, a model card for a specific model architecture was compiled as shown in Figure 12. It contains performance metrics, development information, limitations, fairness and privacy concerns, among other information.

Figure 12: Example model card for UC1.

In addition to the model cards, the Athena project also proposes a data card template which was developed in WP2. Data cards complement model cards by providing crucial information about the training data used. This includes details on the data's origin, collection methods, and any annotations applied. Data cards are important for understanding potential biases or limitations inherited by the model from the training data. This transparency is essential for responsible AI development and ensuring the trustworthiness of the final models which were trained with the corresponding dataset. An example data card for the models used in UC1 was also developed in WP2 and is depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Example data card for nuScenes dataset.

For the final UC1 demonstrator the goal is to create a model and data card for all key models that are deployed in the real-world demonstrator.

2.3. Outlook for the 2nd cycle (IKA)

In summary, we evaluated the current mechanisms, models and approaches for UC1 and determined their respective metrics. The UC1 offline demonstration is a composition of a robust and reliable object detector architecture, explainable layer mechanisms, model uncertainty quantification and an XAI-interface. The explainability and transparency of the models are supported by model and data cards as an additional information source.

The final UC1 demonstrator will be a real-world demonstrator that runs with live sensor data. A real-time capable multi-modal detector model with proven high accuracy and robustness scores should be used. In future, IKA wants to improve uncertainty quantification (UQ) for this query-based object detector and integrate the uncertainty measure into the XAI interface as additional information for the user. The XAI interface will be implemented in ROS RVIZ which would allow a real-time usage in the demonstrator. Additionally, model and data cards will be used to communicate the performance evaluation of the model, development, and usage information, as well as the data's origin, collection methods, and any annotations applied.

2.4. Results of the evaluation in the 1st cycle (Valeo)

A precise and accurate classification of traffic signs is of great importance for trustworthy perception because traffic signs are an important part of road traffic. Germany alone has around 680 different traffic, hazard, regulation, and direction signs.

If you look beyond national borders, there are many more traffic signs. In addition, the appearance of the same traffic signs, i.e., with the same meaning, can change slightly too drastically. In addition, new traffic signs are regularly added to the roads.

Creating a training data set for a DNN for traffic sign classification with all existing traffic signs across national borders is an extremely complex and difficult undertaking.

This makes it even more crucial to have a DNN with a very high generalization capability to classify traffic signs that were not present in the training data. This type of generalization capability can be attributed to the CLIP model [6]. In this WP, the CLIP model was evaluated for its generalization ability for unseen classes (i.e., classes are not present in the training dataset).

In total, two experiments were conducted. First, eight classes are randomly selected to be excluded from the training of the CLIP model. Second, for these eight classes, only a few samples (5 and 20) are used for training to evaluate how many samples are needed to successfully "retrain" with new traffic signs. Normally, there are about 50 to a few hundred samples per class.

To train the CLIP model, a combination of three publicly available datasets with a traffic sign classification in their ground truth data: GTSRB [7], ZOD [8], MAPILLARY [9] were used. Classes that are present in two or all three datasets are combined so that the total number of classes is 280.

Figure 14 shows the inverted top-1 and top-5 error rates achieved for experiments 1 and 2. The upper number is the inverted top-1 error rate, and the lower is the inverted top-5 error rate within a cell.

The inverse of the top-1 and top-5 error rates in image classification represents the accuracy of the model, indicating the proportion of images correctly classified within the top-ranked prediction (top-1) or within the top five predictions (top-5) respectively.

The results show that CLIP partially classifies the traffic signs correctly in 7 of the 8 cases, although they were not included in the training data (see third column).

If five samples per class are added to the training data, most classes' error rate improves significantly (see fourth column). In the case of the 20 samples (see fifth column), the inverted error rate improves further so that for domestic animals, for example, 100% is achieved in the inverted top 5 error rate.

For the "weight limit with trucks" class, it should be noted that there are only 20 total samples, which explains the slightly higher inverted top-5 error rate in column five.

GZM	280 classes	272 classes	280 classes, 5 samples	280 classes, 20 samples
Except bicycles	77.78	10.11	47.44	70.45
	100	43.70	86.86	99.86
Maximum speed limit 55	78.60	20.58	58.34	76.82
	96.36	66.91	90.91	96.24
No left turn	86.50	24.33	67.98	74.12
	97.38	45.28	88.76	93.58
Weight limit with trucks	4.58	0	1.82	5.90
	14.45	0	8.39	16.78
Triple lanes turn left center lane	66.70	8.32	52.31	52.61
	100	51.22	88.99	93.57
Domestic animals	100	33.21	59.86	89.54
	100	64.20	82.65	100
Railroad intersection	94.41	28.21	46.72	87.25
	100	56.87	88.78	98.82
End of overtaking	66.75	6.77	29.52	62.74
	100	18.78	59.69	97.26

Figure 14: Inverted top-1 and top-5 error rate for CLIP on GZM (GTSRB, ZOD and MAPILLARY).

All in all, without having a single sample in the training data, it is possible in most cases to classify the traffic sign, but only with a low accuracy. If only five samples are added, the accuracy improves significantly, and 20 samples are sometimes sufficient for a 100% inverted top-5 error rate. These findings show that the generalization capability of CLIP must be further enhanced to achieve reliable traffic sign recognition for unseen classes. A more advanced weight fusion strategy could help at this point. However, only a few samples are often sufficient to achieve very high accuracy.

2.5. Setup (SIE-NL)

The safety assurance of AI-enabled sensing and perception subsystems utilized in autonomous vehicles are of paramount importance in ensuring the safe and reliable operation of automated driving systems.

According to the ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI (EU-study/report, 2019) the development, deployment and use of AI systems should meet the seven key requirements for trustworthy AI: (1) human agency and oversight, (2) technical robustness and safety, (3) privacy and data governance, (4) transparency, (5) diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, (6) environmental and societal well-being and (7) accountability.

Therefore, one of the investigations presented hereby is related to technical robustness and safety considering diversity, non-discrimination and fairness. In this sense, the robustness of the sensing and perception stack is studied, when different vulnerable road users, which belong to different age, gender and ethnic categories are considered. The safety assurance of AI-enabled sensing and perception subsystems utilized in autonomous vehicles are of paramount importance in ensuring the safe and reliable operation of automated driving systems.

Furthermore, with focus on building a fault-tolerant safety architecture, by implementing a runtime safety assurance approach, Siemens Industry Software Netherlands investigated topics associated with the safety assurance of sensing and perception subsystems. Specifically, we investigated the robustness and sensitivity of AI-based sensing and perception subsystems in a systematic manner. The findings shed light on parameters influencing object detection robustness, such as object size, weather conditions, and illumination.

Figure 15 illustrates a block diagram of an autonomous vehicle's system architecture, which includes a redundant safety loop. The safety loop incorporates multi-modal sensing for diversity and diagnostics, although it is not explicitly depicted in the figure. Under this configuration, if the primary controller violates a safety condition, the backup controller takes charge and initiates an emergency maneuver. In addition, the safety loop is equipped with backup sensors, a backup controller, vehicle actuators, and a diagnostic mechanism to detect failures. In the event of a failure, the diagnostic mechanism triggers the primary controller to execute an emergency maneuver, as shown by the dotted line connecting the diagnostic mechanism to the primary controller in the diagram.

The emergency maneuver can be described as follows:

- an emergency stop, in the same lane
- a lane change, to the emergency lane (or side of the road) and stop in the emergency lane (or side of the road)
- a lane change, to the emergency lane and operation with limited performance (low speed) to the nearest garage.

Figure 15: Overall safety concept – primary and back-up controller.

The runtime assurance (RTA) safety mechanism offers a significant benefit in its design, which involves the independent verification of the backup controller and the primary controller. The separation allows the RTA to give priority to safety, while the primary controller concentrates on performance. A beneficial aspect of this approach is the capability to evaluate novel control

algorithms (primary controller) on pre-existing hardware without compromising safety or requiring additional certification [10].

Furthermore, the backup controller, which is generally less complex than performance-oriented controller, provides simpler and more cost-effective procedures for verification, validation, and certification. While the idea of separating safety and control loops is not novel in the industry, there is often a lack of comprehensive mathematical explanation and formal verification of the interplay between primary and backup controllers.

In autonomous vehicles, identifying and addressing faults is of utmost importance, especially in systems critical for safety. This is accomplished by incorporating redundancies to ensure the detection of failures in the event of system malfunction.

When choosing a safety architecture, it is essential to consider both reliability and complexity of the system. The complexity is assessed by considering the quantity of components necessary for constructing the safety architecture. This factor is crucial as it has a significant influence on the cost, efficiency, and maintainability of the system.

Based on the previous theoretical and practical considerations, the proposed safety loop architecture is shown in Figure 16. The backup sensing and perception subsystem utilizes a 2oo3 (two out of three) design, which guarantees high reliability by employing triple modular redundancy. This configuration enables uninterrupted operation even in the event of a single module failure. Simultaneously, the decision and control subsystems employ a 1oo2D architecture, which enhances safety by incorporating diagnostic capabilities.

Figure 16: Backup sensors and backup controller in the safety loop

Results of the evaluation in the 1st cycle (SIE-NL)

Autonomous vehicles incorporate a range of sensors, such as cameras, radars, and LiDAR, each providing different advantages to create a comprehensive perspective of the surroundings. Cameras are highly proficient in detecting and analysing object characteristics, which is crucial for tasks such as recognizing traffic signs. Radars effectively capture object motion details with high resolution, while LiDAR provides extensive coverage and precise ranging capabilities. While radar is highly resilient in unfavourable conditions, cameras may encounter difficulties with fluctuating lighting, and LiDAR might exhibit reduced effectiveness in severe weather [11]. By integrating these sensors through sensor fusion, the detection and perception capabilities are improved, resulting in a more precise interpretation of the surrounding environment for the vehicle.

Currently, we assessed the robustness of the sensing and perception subsystem. This subsystem employs YOLOv3, a Deep Neural Network (DNN), in the Simcenter Prescan [12] [simulation environment, as illustrated in Figure 17. The YOLOv3 model, which has been trained on the extensive COCO dataset consisting of 80 distinct object categories, plays a pivotal role in the tasks of detecting and classifying objects [13].

The accuracy of YOLOv3's output was rigorously validated by comparing it frame by frame with reference ground truth data in extended KITTI format (see Table 1). The knowledge acquired from this investigation, which is based on simulation, serves as the basis for creating algorithms that can detect faults. These algorithms are essential for the experimental use of multiple sensing methods in autonomous vehicles.

Figure 17: A snapshot from Simcenter Prescan simulation environment.

Table 1: Data structure – extended KITTI format

Values	Name	Description
1	object ID	Unique object ID from Prescan
1	object type	Describes the type of the object based on Simcenter Prescan object types

#Values	Name	Description
1	type	Describes the type of object: 'Car', 'Van', 'Truck', 'Pedestrian', 'Person_sitting', 'Cyclist', 'Tram', 'Misc' or 'DontCare'
1	truncated	Float from 0 (non-truncated) to 1 (truncated), where truncated refers to the object leaving image boundaries
1	occluded	Integer (0,1,2,3) indicating occlusion state: 0 = fully visible, 1 = partly occluded 2 = largely occluded, 3 = unknown
1	alpha	Observation angle of object, ranging $[-\pi, \pi]$
4	bbox	2D bounding box of object in the image (0-based index): contains left, top, right, bottom pixel coordinates
3	dimensions	3D object dimensions: height, width, length (in meters)
3	location	3D object location x,y,z in camera coordinates (in meters)
1	rotation_y	Rotation ry around Y-axis in camera coordinates $[-\pi, \pi]$
1	score	Only for results: Float, indicating confidence in detection, needed for p/r curves, higher is better.

Furthermore, the objects – in terms of detection difficulties – have been classified in {Easy, Moderate, Difficult}. This classification is shown in Table 2 and is based on object size, truncation and occlusion.

Table 2: Object classes based on detection difficulties.

		Truncation	Occlusion			
			0	1	2	3
Object size (ratio)	> 0.05 Large	< 0.2	Easy	Easy	Easy	Difficult
		[0.2, 0.5]	Easy	Easy	Moderate	Difficult
		> 0.5	Easy	Moderate	Difficult	Difficult
	[0.025, 0.05] Medium	< 0.2	Easy	Easy	Moderate	Difficult
		[0.2, 0.5]	Easy	Moderate	Difficult	Difficult
		> 0.5	Moderate	Difficult	Difficult	Difficult
	< 0.025 Small	< 0.2	Easy	Moderate	Difficult	Difficult
		[0.2, 0.5]	Moderate	Difficult	Difficult	Difficult
		> 0.5	Difficult	Difficult	Difficult	Difficult

During the simulations different weather and illumination conditions have been created in Simcenter Prescan environment as shown in Figure 18.

Furthermore, since one of the objectives is to investigate the sensitivity of the object detection and classification algorithm considering different vulnerable road users (VRUs), we considered 5 different VRUs as follows: VRUs = {'Male Regular', 'Female with Buggy', 'Male Cycling Cyclist', 'Female with Shopping Cart', 'Child Regular'} [14].

Figure 18: Different weather and illumination conditions created in Simcenter Prescan

The robustness assessment has been done comparing the YOLOv3 detections with the ground truth data from Simcenter Prescan, as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Robustness assessment of AI-based sensing and perception subsystems.

Furthermore, the evaluation of object association's precision is performed using a metric known as Intersection Over Union (IoU). IoU is a metric that measures the extent to which two bounding boxes overlap. A higher IoU value, which signifies more overlap, demonstrates superior precision in YOLOv3's object detection. Thus, in this situation, IoU functions are an essential metric for assessing the ability of YOLOv3 to precisely detect and align 2D bounding boxes with those in the ground truth data.

The analysis indicates that the validation accuracy of YOLOv3 generally declines with higher depth thresholds (where depth is the distance between the ego vehicle and the detected object). Nevertheless, when the depth threshold is increased, the accuracy diminishes because there is a higher occurrence of misdetections, particularly for smaller objects that become less detectable at larger distances in a two-dimensional perspective. When it comes to lighting conditions, higher accuracy is noticed during the middle of the day, specifically at 10:00, 12:00, and 15:00, as opposed to the early morning and evening hours at 07:00 and 19:00. These findings indicate that YOLOv3 exhibits superior performance in well-illuminated environments, while its accuracy decreases in low-light conditions, as shown in Figure 20.

Furthermore, in Figure 20, we observe that the validation accuracy is decreasing as the depth thresholds are decreasing, with one exception for $\text{Depth} \leq 10[\text{m}]$ where the validation accuracy is below the validation accuracy of $\text{Depth} \leq 20[\text{m}]$. Based on our investigations, this is mainly due to two things: field of view of the camera and the current scenario set-up. Thus, in our current scenario, we have a very limited number of targets, what remain in the field of view of the camera, below the depth threshold $\text{Depth} \leq 10[\text{m}]$ (they exit the camera field of view, before reaching the threshold).

Additionally, as shown in Figure 21, it is apparent that the validation accuracy is highest for objects that are easily detectable, and it decreases for objects that are of moderate or difficult nature. The pattern remains consistent as the depth thresholds increase, with a significant decrease in validation accuracy [15].

Figure 20: Validation accuracy function on illumination, weather, and depth.

Figure 21: Validation accuracy and IoU function on object classes.

Outlook for the 2nd cycle (SIE-NL)

For the 2nd cycle the following main activities are targeted:

- Extend the existing synthetic data set with physics-based radar and physics-based lidar sensors, also considering the weather effects in case of radar and lidar sensor (e.g. signal attenuation factor).
- Generate the synthetic data set in OpenLabel format, too – in collaboration with Vicomtech. The results and the progress made is going to be disseminated in the direction of ASAM.
- In addition, the following research topics are going to be investigated:
- How to use synthetic data during DNNs training and validation – in collaboration with TU/e.
- Further investigate safety architectures for robust, reliable sensing and perception systems considering multimodal sensing, investigate robust depth estimation algorithms, multiple target tracking algorithms using sensor fusion at object level. Here, we plan to work closer together with Continental, IKA and other partners.

3. UC2.1 - AI extended Situation Awareness/Understanding – Collision prediction with Hybrid AI data fusion models

This use case focuses on the ability of a system to provide higher semantics on a driving scene description. Often, systems under test focus on low-semantics concepts, such as the presence of objects of interest (pedestrians, cars, curbs, traffic signs), with information about features, such as physical position, size, or velocity. Such properties are sufficient for a perception system to function and provide safety to a CCAM system. For instance, a lane keeping system (LKS) would just require the detection of the position of the lane markings, and perhaps some advanced features like type of line; an automated braking system would focus on the presence and distance to the nearest object/obstacle in the heading direction of the vehicle.

The evaluation of such functions, though, is a task carried out by test engineers, that want to understand under which situations the function performs better or worse. In practice, the work of test engineers may be driven by regulation, customer requests, or other forms of guidance. Under such guidance, a set of situations or scenarios are defined as interesting, either because previous experiences have shown known weaknesses, or because they are the target of new regulations.

Recorded material from vehicles (e.g., video, point cloud) is labelled and stored in scenario databases, from which test engineers can search for specific situations, and then pull the content to use it in evaluation processes (to obtain Key Performance Indicators). The search process can be partially automated, or guided by labels or tags that point into specific parts of the recording where the scenario of interest has happened. It is expected that scenarios of interest may grow in complexity, beyond the simple presence, position or size of objects, but implying interaction between objects, relationships between relative speeds, relative positions, observed trajectories, etc. Therefore, scenario tags may simplify the searching process only if these tags can grasp these semantic complexities, otherwise the search process becomes a manual (and time consuming) activity, spanning all material until content is found. On the other hand, KPI reports are richer if they contain higher semantic scenario tags, contributing to the ability of the consumers (test engineers) to understand the report and get a deeper understanding of the functioning of the system.

As a mirrored use case, machine learning engineers, building the system, may use the exact same process to identify weaknesses, or focus on re-training ML models to better perform under very specific circumstances.

3.1. Setup

The use case has been implemented following the rationale described in Deliverable D1.2, section 4.2.

As a summary, the approach followed to set-up the use case is the following:

1. Selecting a dataset of road scenes, with recorded images, LIDAR or other sensorial data, which is already labelled at perception-level, i.e., it contains sufficiently rich object-level data, such as the presence, position and class of objects around the ego-vehicle.

2. Production of a semantic data model is devised to semantically model relationships between objects, using ASAM OpenLabel 1.0.0 as labelling format due to its inherent capabilities to model semantic relationships.
3. Convert the object-level annotations of the selected dataset into the semantically enriched data model.
4. Define edge-cases of interest (Note: it is essential to make sure the dataset contains some).
5. Develop the Semantic Labeling System (SLS) and load the semantically enriched data into the SLS.
6. Prepare semantic queries addressing the edge-cases.
7. Run the semantic queries against the SLS and verify the results are the expected edge-cases.

Figure 22: Semantic labeling pipeline.

In Figure 22 the semantic labelling pipeline is illustrated. From left to right, and following the steps abovementioned, datasets are selected, converted into the semantic data model, augmented, and stored into the graphical database, so semantic queries can be executed.

In this 1st cycle we have implemented the entire pipeline, focusing on the following elements:

- **Selection and conversion of nuScenes dataset to OpenLabel** – selected as one of the most complete open-source multi-sensor dataset, with camera, LIDAR, and object-level labels.
- **Creation of Ontology adapted to OpenLabel data model and nuScenes labels** – the work implied the elaboration of a class mapping between the taxonomy of nuScenes, and the OpenLabel schema.
- **Adaption of a visualization tool to nuScenes raw data** – the WebLabel tool by Vicomtech was adapted to load raw data (videos, point cloud, odometry) from the nuScene dataset, in order to visualize and navigate easily through the dataset, and to validate the search process.
- **Implementation of a graph database** – the OpenLabel-converted labels of the nuScene dataset was pushed into a GraphDB database.

- **Creation of SPARQL queries to find specific content** – in this 1st cycle we have focused on simple manoeuvres and situations, to validate the concept.
 - Hard acceleration
 - Hard deceleration
 - Lane change
- **Deployment of a dashboard to explore database** – using GraphDB dashboard to explore the data model, and to run queries.

In parallel, using real and synthetic data, TUE and IDIADA have been working on developing a collision risk prediction model for edge cases, using also data collected on IDIADA test track focusing on VRU scenarios.

3.2. Results of the evaluation in the 1st cycle

In this first cycle the focus was on building up the concepts of the semantic labelling pipeline, as explained in previous section.

The focus has, therefore, been on the functionality, rather than on the volume of the experimentation. For practical reasons, the nuScenes dataset has been chosen, that is sufficiently rich and large to represent modern datasets that might be subject of testing activities as those described by this Use Case.

Next paragraphs illustrate the work carried out, and some preliminary results already obtained on this dataset with the specific set of maneuvers of interest.

GraphDB Data model

GraphDB was chosen to load the built nuScenes ontology, along with the OpenLabel-converted nuScenes labels. GraphDB has a dashboard web application that can be used for several purposes, such as explore the data model (see figures below), including the classes of the taxonomy, but also richer exploration of the relationships between them.

Figure 23 shows the type of visualization of GraphDB. higher-level classes (as circles) contain other lower-level classes, e.g. :Adult is inside :Pedestrian. The area of the circle depicts how many instances of such class exist in the database. In this exercise, this was the number of instances of the class within the nuScenes dataset.

Figure 23: GraphDB dashboard to explore the OpenLabel-adapted nuScenes Taxonomy.

SPARQL Queries

The GraphDB database permits to run SPARQL queries, that were crafted to explore the entire dataset, and to find specific situations.

The following snippets showcase the SPARQL queries implemented to find “Hard acceleration”, “Hard deceleration”, and “Ego Lane Change” manoeuvres. As shown below, the queries are built as sets of semantic triplets, i.e. the higher-level semantics of the target concept are unwrapped as smaller, logical triplets, which executed all together filter out content until all triplets are met.

Ego lane change

```

PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX : <http://www.semanticweb.org/ikontopodis/ontologies/2022/10/untitled-ontology-193#>

SELECT ?f1 ?f2 ?s ?l1 ?l2

WHERE {
  ?l1 rdf:type :Lane .
  ?l2 rdf:type :Lane .
  ?s rdf:type :Scene .
  ?ed1 rdf:type :EgoData .
  ?ed2 rdf:type :EgoData .
  ?s :hasObject ?l1 .
  ?s :hasObject ?l2 .
  ?ed1 :framestamp ?f1 .
  ?ed2 :framestamp ?f2 .
  ?s :hasEgoData ?ed1 .
  ?s :hasEgoData ?ed2 .
  ?ed1 :isLocatedIn ?l1 .
  ?ed2 :isLocatedIn ?l2 .
  ?l1 :isNextTo ?l2 .
  BIND (?f2 - ?f1 AS ?f_dif)
  FILTER (?f_dif = 1)
  FILTER (?f2 > ?f1)
  FILTER (?l1 != ?l2)
}

```

Hard acceleration

```

PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX : <http://www.semanticweb.org/ikontopodis/ontologies/2022/10/untitled-ontology-193#>
PREFIX f: <http://www.ontotext.com/sparql/functions/>

SELECT DISTINCT ?ed ?s ?f ?hypot
WHERE {
  ?s rdf:type :Scene .
  ?ed rdf:type :EgoData .
  ?s :hasEgoData ?ed .
  ?ed :framestamp ?f .
  ?ed :accelX ?ax .
  ?ed :accelY ?ay .
  BIND (f:hypot(?ax, ?ay) AS ?hypot)
  FILTER (?hypot >= 2.5)
  FILTER (?ax > 0)
}

```

Hard deceleration

```

PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX : <http://www.semanticweb.org/ikontopodis/ontologies/2022/10/untitled-ontology-193#>
PREFIX f: <http://www.ontotext.com/sparql/functions/>

```

```

SELECT DISTINCT ?ed ?s ?f ?hypot
WHERE {
?s rdf:type :Scene .
?ed rdf:type :EgoData .
?s :hasEgoData ?ed .
?ed :framestamp ?f .
?ed :accelX ?ax .
?ed :accelY ?ay .
BIND (f:hypot(?ax, ?ay) AS ?hypot)
  FILTER (?hypot >= 3)
  FILTER (?ax < 0)
}

```

As a result, specific frames (timestamps) of the dataset are found, corresponding to the manoeuvres that have been targeted. The specific number of scenarios and frames found can be seen in Table 3. In the case of the Ego lane change manoeuvre, only the exact instant when the manoeuvre happens is identified, thus, the number of scenarios can be extracted, but the number of frames is not considered.

Table 3: Extracted scenarios and frames.

Manoeuvre	N. Scenarios	N. Frames
Ego lane change	107	-
Hard acceleration	37	80
Hard deceleration	25	47
Total in Dataset	850	34000

The nuScenes dataset contains 850 scenes with annotations. In this exercise they were all augmented using the proposed semantic data model. After running the rules, 107 instances of “Ego lane change” manoeuvres, 37 “Hard acceleration”, and 25 “Hard deceleration” have been found. More rules can be added, but haven’t yet been implemented: these could focus on more specific situations, such as a pedestrian approaching a zebra cross, an intersection with specific traffic light status and vehicle movements, etc.

WebLabel visualization

After the extraction of scenarios, the dataset can be visualised to investigate the situation. See Figure 24 below. An interesting “Ego Lane Change” manoeuvre was found. It represents a difficult situation where a set of vehicles are blocking the ego-lane (vehicles green, and pink on the top-view), and there is a continuous lane marking. The ego vehicle violates the continuous lane marking and performs a lane change to right to continue moving and not get blocked by the parked cars.

Figure 24: Visualization of example “Ego lane change” manoeuvre found in the dataset.

Collision risk prediction using real-synthetic data

TUE designed an AI model trained on purely simulated data and assessed collision risk on real-life data provided by IDIADA. The model successfully generalizes to the real-life data and shows promising results. Figure 25 compare the result of the RiskNet with manually annotated video of car to bike turning scenario. The below blue bar indicated the risk moment that is manually annotated while the above yellow bar indicated the result (risk moment) of our RiskNet model.

Figure 25: Collision risk prediction validated on IDIADA dataset (car to bike turning scenario)

3.3. Outlook for the 2nd cycle

The intention towards the 2nd cycle is to expand the developed pipeline in its use with larger datasets and create more complex queries.

Additional queries

For instance, it is planned to create queries for the following higher-level semantics:

- Pedestrian in Zebra Cross
- Pedestrian in Road
- Ego Lane Change
- Vehicle Cut-in
- Vehicle Cut-out
- Lane invasion

During the implementation of these queries, discover new, combined queries might be discovered, depending on their existence in the dataset. For instance, situations where more than one of those situations are encountered happen simultaneously, e.g. “Pedestrian in Road & Vehicle cut-in”. These combinations can expand the semantic capabilities of the developed system, without the need to modify or implement any additional software update.

Extended semantics

At the moment the nuScenes taxonomy is used as a reference. However, the utilisation of the ASAM OpenLabel data model does permit to incorporate additional taxonomies, by means of creating the necessary class mappings. For example, it is aimed to incorporate other large datasets, either open-source (such as the Waymo dataset, nuPlan, or the Vicomtech’s DMD).

Also, depending on the availability of data created within the AITHENA consortium, and the availability of object-level labels, specific queries could be easily created to exercise with other use cases.

Collision risk prediction using real-synthetic data

For next steps, TUE will validate our model on more IDIADA datasets. We will also use and apply Grad-CAM techniques [16] to the RiskNet module to visually explain which actor in the seen/scenario has activated and triggered the risk situation.

4. UC2.2 - AI extended Situation Awareness/Understanding - Robust Prediction modules for Robo-taxis in urban environment

In this use case the focus is on situation awareness. In interactive urban traffic environments vehicles, pedestrians and other traffic participants navigate on highly complex road networks under a variety of environmental conditions while interacting with different kinds of road users. In this context motion planning can only guarantee safety of all participants, if the characteristics of the scenarios are acknowledged.

There are several complex parts involved in achieving this goal, which made it necessary to split this work on to different partners of the Althena consortium. In Figure 26 an overview of these steps and the partner contribution can be seen. In the first cycle of the project, it was planned that each partner is working on his part(s). The results of the evaluation of this work will be shown in this chapter. In the second cycle these parts will be integrated into one demonstrator and the result of the evaluation of the complete system will then be reported in D5.3.

Figure 26: Overview on partners contributions and demonstration parts.

4.1. Setup (TTTA)

TTTA: Robust and accurate timing characteristics of software components jointly implementing situational awareness are crucial to guarantee safe operation of Robo-taxis thus influencing their perceived additional value to individuals and society. The timing characteristics of software components depend on the embedded time-triggered runtime and adequate timing information provided by the owners of each software component. The embedded time-triggered runtime ensures robust and accurate timing characteristic of software components by enforcing deterministic timing and temporal isolation between software components. Deterministic timing of a software component refers to the predictability of periodic activities, i.e., the instants at which a software component performs a certain action are known apriori, before the operation of the system. Temporal isolation is a property of a runtime guaranteeing that the execution of software components has no effect on each other in the time domain, e.g., one software component missing a deadline should not delay the execution of co-located software components.

TTTA provides a controlled execution environment to evaluate timing determinism and the temporal isolation of the embedded time-triggered runtime (c.f. D5.1, Section 3.2, SCEN_01). TTTA evaluates the embedded time-triggered runtime on an industrial-grade edge computing device with an Intel Atom E3950 CPU with four cores at 1.59GHz each and 8GiB of main memory. As the time-triggered embedded runtime is Linux-based, the edge computing device ran Ubuntu server 22.04.1 with Linux kernel v5.9.1 and time-triggered scheduling enabled [17]

Figure 27: Experimental setup to evaluate embedded time-triggered runtime [17]

TTTA evaluates the predictability and temporal isolation of software components executing on the embedded runtime by measuring the end-to-end latency of two containers 0 and 1 exchanging measurement packets via virtual Ethernet devices interconnected by a default Linux software bridge as shown in Figure 27 (c.f. D5.1, Section 3.1, REQ_2.2). The embedded time-triggered runtime dispatches both sender and receiver applications inside the containers according to a static schedule table on the same processor core. Furthermore, the schedule table contains entries to dispatch 15 additional real-time tasks that compete for the CPU resource. Lastly, there are two containers running as background tasks scheduled with the Linux kernel’s Completely Fair Scheduler (CFS) and FIFO Scheduler (fixed priorities). Container 2 scheduled with CFS introduces background load using the stress-ng utility and container 3 generates load for the Linux bridge using a ping flood. We repeated experiments 12 times, and each experiment ran for 10 minutes yielding a total runtime of 2 hours per scenario (no load vs. load).

4.2. Results of the evaluation in the 1st cycle (TTTA)

If the embedded time-triggered runtime succeeds in providing predictable timing, it is expected to measure an end-to-end latency between containers 0 and 1 that exhibits low jitter and that it can be specified before the system’s runtime as a requirement to schedule table generation. Furthermore, if the embedded time-triggered runtime successfully enforces temporal isolation, a decline in the end-to-end latency should not be seen when introducing interfering workloads.

Figure 28: End-to-end latency in no load vs. load scenario.

Figure 28 compares the baseline scenario, i.e., end-to-end latency measurement without interfering load, with the load scenario featuring competing RT tasks, background CPU load, and the ping flood workload. It can be seen that for the baseline without interfering workloads an end-to-end latency of 3.24ms to 3.49ms between containers 0 and 1 is measured. The expected end-to-end latency, derived from the static schedule table, is 3.1ms, thus the containers end-to-end latency can be predicted within a range of 124 to 349 microseconds (c.f. D5.1, Section 3.3, KPI_03). For the load scenario, a very similar distribution of measured end-to-end latency can be observed, however, there is a single outlier of 13.49ms present. TTTA could identify the source of this outlier in the Linux kernel's object cache for fast memory allocations [17]. For the operation of the embedded time-triggered runtime single outliers are not expected to cause problems since the presented experimental setup pushes the system to its operational limits which is not to be expected in a prototype setup.

4.3. Outlook for the 2nd cycle (TTTA)

So far, we evaluated the embedded time-triggered runtime's fundamental capabilities in providing deterministic timing and temporal isolation indicating that it is already meeting KPI_03. Further, evaluation requires the availability of software components, their timing characteristics (period, WCET estimate), and dependencies between components, so that a static schedule table can be generated to integrate the software components on the time-triggered runtime. With the prototypically integrated system in place, TTTA will be able to evaluate KPI_01, KPI_02, and in more detail KPI_03.

4.4. Setup (IFAG)

IFAG designed and developed a first version of the targeted Situational awareness feature enhanced object detection (SAFEOD) function block using a standardized output interface following the ASAM OSI specification, see Figure 29.

Figure 29: Situational awareness feature enhanced object detection (SAFEOD) function block

Within this specification the object list as the main output was defined as follows:
 Object list specification (Althena contributions marked in **yellow**)

Stationary object

```

  ID
  Base
    Dimension
      Length
      Width
      Height
    Position
      X
      Y
      Z
      Orientation
        Roll
        Pitch
        Yaw
  Class
    Traffic light
      Color
        Red
        Orange
        Green
        Opt. static
        Opt. flickering
  
```

Dynamic object

```

  ID
  Base
    Dimension
      Length
      Width
      Height
    Position
      X
      Y
      Z
      Orientation
        Roll
        Pitch
        Yaw
  Class
    Car
      Active signal lights
      Braking
      Right turn indicated
      Left turn indicated
    Cyclist
    Pedestrian
    Opt. Truck
    Opt. Motorbikes
  
```

All Althena project related developments are highlighted in yellow. The interface on the input side of the SAFEOD function block reads in pictures and video streams in common available formats focusing on the ones used in public available data sets. The targeted object detection solution with situational awareness features used for robust scene understanding/prediction is mainly based on camera data. The following situational awareness features build the core innovation of the SAFEOD function block:

- Traffic light colour detection (red, orange, green)
- Vehicle signal light detection (braking lights, left/right indicator lights)
- Bounding box orientation

To realize those features AI-based algorithms are designed and trained with different publicly available data sets. From algorithmic point of view, all three-feature related object detection models are based on the so called You Only Look Once (YOLO) architecture developed by Ultralytics. Those YOLO architectures exist in different versions characterized by several different strengths and weaknesses. Therefore, we analyzed multiple YOLO architectures to identify the most suitable one for our problem setting. As an initial approach we trained data on versions YOLOv5 and YOLOv7. The YOLO model uses a deep neural network to detect objects in images and videos. It is capable of detecting multiple objects in a single image with high accuracy and speed. YOLOv7 is optimized for real-time object detection applications and is designed to run efficiently on a variety of hardware platforms. One of the key features of YOLOv7 is its ability to handle large datasets with millions of images. The model uses a combination of advanced data augmentation techniques and transfer learning to improve accuracy and reduce training time. Overall, YOLOv7 is a powerful and versatile object detection model that can be used in a wide range of applications, including self-driving cars, surveillance systems, and robotics. YOLOv8 is the latest iteration in the YOLO series of real-time object detectors, offering cutting-edge performance in terms of accuracy and speed. Building upon the advancements of previous YOLO versions, YOLOv8 introduces new features and optimizations that make it an ideal choice for various object detection tasks in a wide range of applications.

4.5. Results of the evaluation in the 1st cycle (IFAG)

The gained results in the first project period are structured along the targeted situational awareness features:

- Traffic light colour detection (red, orange, green)
- Vehicle signal light detection (breaking lights, left/right indicator lights)
- Bounding box orientation

Traffic light colour detection (red, orange, green)

The YOLO architectures used to identify the traffic light colour are trained with two public available data sets: CARLA and LISA. CARLA includes over 2500 images of traffic lights defined by colour: red, green, yellow and black. Class 'black' indicates looking at the traffic light from the back or from the side. Images were gathered from CARLA, which is an open-source autonomous driving simulator. LISA on the other side include real-world data including many traffic lights collected in San Diego, California, USA. The database provides four daytime and two night-time sequences, including different weather conditions such as rain and fog, primarily used for testing, providing 23 minutes and 25 seconds of driving in Pacific Beach and La Jolla, San Diego.

To evaluate the performance of the trained YOLO architectures we used the well-known and widely spread Confusion Matrix, Precision-Recall Curve, mean Average Precision (mAP), intersection over union (IoU) and the F-1 Curve/score as main metrics and KPIs to also make our results comparable to other in that domain.

Figure 30 to Figure 32 outline exemplarily the gained results during the first project period. Figure 30 shows the so-called Precision Recall curve. A precision-recall curve shows the tradeoff between precision and recall for different threshold. The goal is to reach a maximum area under the curve representing both a high recall and a high precision, where high precision relates to a low false positive rate, and high recall relates to a low false negative rate. In that sense, the best results were achieved for the detection of green traffic lights, see Figure 30. Some potential reasons for that are related to the fact that red and orange colors are visually closer to each other than green and orange/red, typically data sets include less orange coloured traffic lights than red and green ones, and red and orange lights can also occur in different background situations such as breaking or

indicator signals from other traffic participants. To overcome the issue mentioned the training data set will be extended accordingly in the second project period.

Figure 30: Precision-Recall Curve for traffic light colour detection.

The F1 Confidence Curve shown in Figure 31 plots the F1 score against different confidence thresholds. A higher F1 score indicates better performance, and the confidence threshold at which the F1 score is maximized is often considered the optimal threshold for making predictions. Again, the best results were achieved for green traffic lights.

Figure 31: F1-Confidence Curve for traffic light colour detection.

The detected traffic light colours are depicted with the detected class itself and the related confidence value, see Figure 32.

Figure 32: Traffic light colour detection.

Table 4 depicts the evaluated metrics and KPIs for the traffic light colour detection. For our data set YOLOv5 had shown better performance compared to v7 except F1 score. Moreover, v5 model showed less bias for majority class and less time for training compared to v7, see values in the Table 4. YOLOv8 had shown better performance compared to V5 and V7. Moreover, YOLOv8 model showed less bias for majority class and more mAP for training compared to YOLOv5.

Table 4: Evaluated metrics and KPIs for the traffic light colour detection.

Metric for 100 epochs	YOLOv8	YOLOv7	YOLOv5
mAP @.50 (at 50% confidence)	58.6	22	40
mAP @.95 (at 95% confidence)	22	17	25
Efficiency F1 score	62	60	48
Confidence based on IoU	48	33	45-60
Time for training (on colab)	54 min	2 hours	25 min

Vehicle signal light detection (breaking lights, left/right indicator lights)

The YOLO architectures used to identify vehicle signal lights are trained using two publicly available datasets: LISA and Kitti. The Kitti dataset includes an object detection and object orientation estimation benchmark, which consists of 7481 training images and 7518 test images, comprising a total of 80,256 labelled objects. All images are in colour and saved as PNG, including many activated vehicle signal lights.

The performance of the trained YOLO architectures was evaluated using the same metrics and KPIs as those used for traffic light colour detection.

Figure 33 to Figure 35 exemplify the results obtained during the first project period. Figure 33 displays the Precision-Recall curve, highlighting highly precise results for the detection of braking signals. However, the situation is much more complex for the left and right turn indicators. The orange signal depicts the performance for the left and right turn indicators. Both classes are merged into a single class as their performance is very similar.

Figure 33: Precision-Recall Curve for the vehicle signal light detection.

Figure 34 displays the confusion matrix for the vehicle signal detection feature. The matrix shows the number of correct predictions, including true positives (TP) and true negatives (TN), as well as model errors in the form of false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN). The results indicate that the braking signal detection achieved the best performance.

Figure 34: Confusion Matrix for the vehicle signal light detection.

Figure 35 shows the detected braking signals along with their corresponding class and confidence value.

Figure 35: Vehicle signal light detection.

Table 5 shows the evaluated metrics and KPIs for the vehicle signal light detection. The model is biased towards the braking signal class due to the fewer images of activated left and right turn indicators. To reduce this bias, we labelled more objects of the left/right turn indicator class. The model performs well with a mAP of 0.79 at a 1.0 confidence score. However, the model is struggling to accurately detect activated left and right turn indicators, while its ability to detect braking signals is good. Despite increasing the number of labels for turn indicators, the model still cannot detect the class with certainty. This confusion may be due to the similarities in colour, between the orange turn indicators and the red braking signals, and the challenge how much frames we have to consider to distinguish between static (braking lights) and blinking lights (left/right turn indicator lights). This observation is confirmed by a reduction in the KPI mAP.

Table 5: Evaluated metrics and KPIs for the vehicle signal light detection.

Metric for 200 Iterations	YOLOv5	YOLOv8
mAP @.55 (at 55% confidence)	53.6 %	80 %
mAP @.95 (at 95% confidence)	43 %	60%
Efficiency F1 score	48%	88 %
Confidence based on IoU	45-60	85-90
Time for training (on colab)	25 min	25min
Recall	73.5%	65.5%

Bounding box orientation

The YOLO architectures used to identify the bounding box orientation were trained using two publicly available datasets: CityScapes and Eurocity. CityScapes is a large-scale dataset that contains a diverse set of stereo video sequences recorded in street scenes from 50 different cities. It has high-quality pixel-level annotations for 5,000 frames, in addition to a larger set of 20,000 weakly annotated frames. In contrast, the Eurocity dataset focuses on people in urban traffic scenes. EuroCity Persons is a person dataset that has been manually labeled in over 47,300 images, with over 238200-person instances. This dataset is almost ten times larger than previous person datasets used for benchmarking. The dataset was recorded throughout Europe, providing diversity.

To evaluate the performance of the trained YOLO architectures, we used the same metrics and KPIs as for traffic light colour detection and vehicle signal light detection.

Figure 36 to Figure 38 exemplify the results obtained during the first project period. Figure 36 displays the Precision-Recall curve, highlighting precise results for the detection of bounding box orientation for all object classes except cyclists. Cyclist orientation appears to be the most challenging aspect of the bounding box orientation feature.

Figure 36: Precision-Recall curve for bounding box orientation.

Figure 37 shows the F1 Confidence Curve, which plots the F1 score against different confidence thresholds. The performance of detecting the orientation of cyclists is weaker compared to the other object classes.

Figure 37: F1-Confidence Curve for bounding box orientation.

The orientation of the detected bounding box is indicated by the box itself, which includes a cross to show the front face (refer to Figure 38).

Figure 38: Bounding box orientation.

Table 5 shows the evaluated metrics and KPIs for the bounding box orientation detection. The model performs above average, with a mean average precision of 74% and a precision of 94%. However, it struggles to distinguish between cyclists and pedestrians, resulting in more false positives. The YOLOv8 model outperforms the previous version, YOLOv5. However, it still faces some difficulties in accurately predicting low-resolution images. To enhance the model's ability to differentiate between cyclists and pedestrians, it is essential to label more images of the cyclist class. Moreover, training the model on low-resolution images could improve its ability to predict such images.

Table 6: Evaluated metrics and KPIs for the vehicle signal light detection.

Metric for 100 epochs	YOLOv8	YOLOv5
mAP @.50 (at 50% confidence)	74.5%	39 %
mAP @.95 (at 95% confidence)	53.22%	25 %
Efficiency F1 score	69 %	55 %
Confidence based on IoU	66	45-60
Time for training (on colab)	25 min	1 h

4.6. Outlook for the 2nd cycle (IFAG)

IFAG: While the performance of the traffic light colour detection is already quite satisfactory, IFAG will focus in the second project period on further improving the identified problems within the vehicle signal light detection and bounding box orientation. Specifically, the training data used for the detection of activated left/right turn signals will be extended to improve the detection of left/right turn signals compared to brake signals. Furthermore, to improve the model's

performance in discriminating between cyclists and pedestrians in terms of orientation, it is necessary to label more images of the cyclist class.

4.7. Setup (SIE-BE)

The main objective of UC-2.2 demonstrator is to create realistic datasets that will be used for the development and validation of machine learning algorithms, related to the motion prediction of traffic participants. These algorithms will ensure the safe and anticipatory operation of autonomous taxi robots.

The main contribution of SIE-BE in this UC was to generate a multi-modal time-synchronized driving dataset, utilizing their existing data acquisition system as it was described in D5.1. The purpose of generating such dataset was to validate machine learning models and construct safety-critical synthetic driving scenarios that will be used in a HuiL and ViL setup. To achieve this, a number of filtering and data cleaning processes have been applied to the dataset in order to be given as input to a perception pipeline for extracting information of the lane network, traffic signs/lights and actors from the environment. The result of the perception pipeline is then fed as input to a template-based driving scenario detector to keep only relevant safety-critical scenarios out of huge amounts of recorded data, and then the selected scenario is constructed synthetically in Simcenter Prescan using the sensor data generated from the vehicle setup.

4.8. Results of the evaluation of the 1st cycle (SIE-BE)

The first step towards importing such realistic scenarios into Simcenter Prescan, is to create a local map, where all ego poses of the vehicle with respect to a fixed GPS coordinate were extracted from the Septentrio GNSS/IMU device. Secondly, a YOLOv7 object detector was utilized to detect traffic signs/lights from camera data during the recordings (Figure 20a). By using the extrinsic transformation of the LiDAR-camera sensors and the intrinsic calibration of the camera, the LiDAR point cloud data were projected in the image and by keeping only the projected LiDAR points that belong to the predicted traffic sign/light 2D bounding box, the relative distance from the ego vehicle is extracted. Then, by combining the ego poses of the ego vehicle in the fixed local map frame with the relative distance of a traffic sign to the vehicle in the local coordinate frame, the traffic signs were placed into the local map frame. The next step was to extract the lane network using LiDAR and camera data. To achieve this the YOLOv2 model was utilised to segment the road lanes (Figure 20b) and then the segmented lane areas were fused in the corresponding LiDAR point cloud data. Then by stacking all these segmented LiDAR point cloud data together using the generated ego poses from the GNSS/IMU device and then performing a clustering algorithm like DBSCAN in the segmented data, the lane network was extracted from the recordings. Finally, an ensemble of 3D LiDAR-based object detectors in combination with a 3D tracking algorithm was used to extract the 3D object list of actors from the environment (Figure 20c).

Figure 20: Output results from the perception pipeline: Left image (a) illustrates a traffic sign prediction result of aYOLOv7 model, middle image shows the lane segmentation results of YOLOPv2 in the camera data (b) and right image (c) highlights the predicted 3D bounding boxes of the actors in the scene.

To generate only safety relevant synthetic driving scenarios in the simulation environment, a template-based driving scenario detector was used to extract driving scenarios. Figure 21 shows an example of extracting lane change and cornering events using the ego lane network information predicted from the perception pipeline. To achieve this, a gradient-based filter is applied to the data to detect the maximum change in ego lane distance that correspond to lane change events and detecting the maximum curvature of the road for the cornering scenarios. Finally, all the results of the perception pipeline and the scenario detection were combined and imported to Simcenter Prescan to create synthetic scenarios from real driving data that later can be used for HuiL/ViL testing (Figure 22).

Figure 21: Visualization of the detected lane change and cornering events for driving scenario extraction.

Figure 22: Demonstration of Real2Sim scenario in Simcenter Prescan.

4.9. Outlook for the 2nd cycle (SIE-BE)

An X-in-the-loop methodology framework is currently in the creation phase to bridge the gap between virtual and physical testing using Simcenter products like Simcenter Testlab RT, Amesim and Prescan. Due to the limited person months in the UC, the approach will be to prepare the setup for ViL testing. The main objective is to understand how the (virtual) vehicle under test responds when a controller uses data generated from Simcenter Prescan and how the developed machine learning model can be deployed on an ECU in real time. For that, tests need to happen first on SIE-BE hexapod environment (Figure 23) to be able to test level 5 experiments quickly and in a safe way.

Figure 23: Demonstration of hexapod environment in the synthetically generated driving scenarios.

4.10. Setup (CAF)

As shown in Figure 26, CAF is involved in the UC2-2 by being asked to deliver and validate numerous computer vision models/algorithms such as freespace detection, object detection, lane detection, fusion for LiDAR and camera and the lane change prediction.

It is worth mentioning that all of CAF's algorithms were tested in a Linux environment, utilizing ROS2 Foxy for establishing connections and facilitating communication. This setup was instrumental for the development and testing of the computer vision models and the integration of LiDAR and camera data. ROS2 Foxy's compatibility with real-time systems and complex robotic applications ensured that the solutions were not only validated in a simulated environment but also primed for real-world application.

4.11. Results of the evaluation from the first cycle (CAF)

Focusing on object detection, our approach initially utilized YOLOv5 but transitioned to YOLO-NAS. The model was trained using a diverse dataset comprising COCO2017 and CAF's internal dataset, totalling 40,000 frames over 300 epochs and capable of detecting up to 80 classes (COCO's classes).

The evaluation methodology employed for our object detection system is meticulously designed to provide precise insights into its capabilities and alignment with the Siemens test dataset's requirements. This process involves two key phases: labels mapping and metrics calculation. During the labels mapping phase, we strive to ensure precise correspondence between the model's output labels and the predefined categories in the test dataset's annotation schema, making necessary adaptations to maintain the integrity of the evaluation process. The evaluation methodology of our object detector consists of different scenarios testing and metrics calculation

to align with the imposed requirements and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in D5.1, including Intersection over Union (IoU), precision, recall, F1 score, and mean Average Precision (mAP), to assess model performance globally. In fact, the model demonstrates strong performance in detecting a wide range of dynamic objects, including trucks, cars, motorbikes, bicycles, and pedestrians (REQ_10), alongside static objects like traffic lights (REQ_11). In terms of KPIs, the model achieves noteworthy scores: a mean average precision (mAP) of 0.79 (KPI_08), an Intersection over Union (IoU) of 0.80 (KPI_09) and a f1-score of 0.80 as well. These metrics underscore the model's effective object detection capabilities and its precise localization of objects within diverse urban traffic scenarios.

Figure 39: An example of the object detection on an image retrieved from the Siemens dataset.

Transitioning to the freespace detection, the algorithm is tailored to identify and map out navigable areas in an environment using sensor data, particularly LiDAR. Initialization of the system with specific parameters such as sensor resolution and range limits enable customized performance. By converting raw 3D points into a polar coordinate system, the algorithm employs geometric principles to categorize the environment into cells and polar rays, facilitating obstacle and free space identification. Given the absence of labelled data for testing, evaluation focused on assessing the computational time required for the algorithm's execution. Furthermore, testing with Siemens data yielded promising results, indicating the algorithm's efficacy in practical scenarios.

Figure 40: An example of an image extracted from the Siemens dataset with the visualization of the output of CAF's Freespace algorithm.

The image above illustrates two views relevant to autonomous vehicle technology: a real-world urban driving scene (left) and its corresponding sensor data visualization (right). The green dot at the center of the right image represents the ego vehicle, oriented toward the front-right, with a detection parameter set to identify objects taller than 0.5 meters (this parameter can be changed). This setting effectively ignores low-height obstacles such as curbs but detects critical entities like pedestrians and vehicles, as shown.

Shifting focus to the fusion algorithm developed by CAF for the same use case, this algorithm combines data from LiDAR sensors and cameras to improve object detection in complex environments. It sets parameters to align LiDAR and camera data, accurately localizes objects within the camera's view, filters out irrelevant data, and maintains consistency across different coordinate systems for a unified understanding of the environment.

Despite the absence of labelled data, here is an example of the results which are promising:

Figure 41: An example of the result of the fusion algorithm on a CARLA scenario.

The visualization above is done in the camera coordinate system, where the object detector identifies two objects: a car and a light. Our algorithm compares this to the 3D detection that we have. Here, the car detection corresponds to an entry in the 3D detection list, resulting in the visualization appearing in green and providing various 3D information in the world coordinate system. However, the light detection does not find its equivalent, resulting in the visualization remaining red without displaying additional information. It is noteworthy that the algorithm operates swiftly; for the previous example, the pipeline took only 0.000018 seconds to complete.

Moving on to the lane detection algorithm, this detector stands out as it utilizes a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to accurately identify lane markings from road images, a departure from the two previous approaches. The process begins with image preprocessing to ensure consistent input for the CNN, adjusting for factors like lighting and contrast. The CNN then analyses the images to detect lane marking features such as edges and shapes, followed by postprocessing to interpret these features and determine lane boundaries. This information, including lane geometry and types, is crucial for navigation and driver assistance systems, showcasing the algorithm's versatility across different driving conditions. This model is based on the logic and labels below for lanes classification on the road.

Figure 42: CAF's Lane Detection labels for Autonomous Vehicles Navigation.

Given the absence of labelled data, we attempted to assess its effectiveness using the Siemens dataset and images retrieved from the internet. An example is given below:

Figure 43: An Example of the Lane Detection output on an image retrieved from Siemens' dataset.

The figure above reflects CAF's Lane Detector output. According to the logic explained, the blue line corresponds to the 'Left Adjacent Lane', the green one to the 'Right Adjacent Lane'. The 'Ego Lane' is represented in red and the 'Road' in grey. We note that the right adjacent lane is not visible as it overlaps with the right red one.

4.12. Outlook for the second cycle (CAF)

For the second cycle, CAF's goal is to continue its development of lane change prediction as well as to improve its models, in particular the object detector, to be able to reach the required f1-score imposed in D5.1. For the moment the tests have been done on the synthetic dataset provided by Siemens but finally, it is planned to test everything on real data. This also implies to make sure that there is not a big gap in the metrics between real and synthetic data (the gap must be less than 10%).

4.13. Setup (VIF)

To attain comprehensive situational awareness of the observed scenario, the robo-taxi must extend its awareness beyond past and current states to include predictions of the future states of its environment. The predictive capability is particularly crucial for scenarios taking place in complex and dynamic urban environments. Designing a motion prediction model according to the anticipated environment enhances the scenario understanding, thereby providing a more reliable input for subsequent motion planning and decision-making. Only with a robust situational awareness can the robo-taxi execute the commands from the decision-making system and, consequently, navigate its environment safely and efficiently.

While motion planning and decision-making components are outside the scope of the UC2.2, it is assumed that such perception components precede the prediction model, providing it with

required scenario observations. However, these scenario observations could be further enhanced before being forwarded to the prediction model. Informing the model of only separate elements of the environment may prove insufficient, particularly in urban settings where numerous relations exist. Therefore, the model would benefit from prior semantic enhancement of the perception output, defining how static and dynamic elements influence one another. A suitable structure capable of capturing diverse environment elements with their respective properties over time, as well as relations between them, is a graph database. To use a graph database as an abstraction of the observed scenario, an ontology tailored to considered urban scenarios is adopted. Lastly, by incorporating tools to manipulate the graph database, a local dynamic map (LDM) is created and utilized for subsequent model input generation.

Following each database update, the essential scenario data required for predicting the motion of the targeted traffic participant is extracted and utilized to generate what is termed intermediate model input. Considering one observed traffic participant at a time, the edges connecting the considered traffic participant's node to nodes representing other environment elements are translated onto a raster using a predefined shape and colour encoding method. Therefore, the intermediate input is represented as a bird's eye view (BEV) raster, encompassing map information and the state history of all traffic participants including the one whose states are to be predicted. It should be noted that assumptions about the scenario data availability were established and have influenced the selection of training and testing datasets. Both real-world (inD) and synthetic (CommonRoad) datasets chosen had to include complete map information with indications of diverse road structures and state recordings of various classes of traffic participants with a focus on vulnerable road users (VRUs). These datasets ensured that standard interactions present in urban environments can be observed and learned by the prediction model.

The scenario data contained in the intermediate inputs holds information about the future states of the observed traffic participants. However, another source of scenario knowledge exists that can be integrated into the prediction model. While the prediction model can learn the laws governing the dynamics of traffic participants, these laws have already been extensively studied and utilized in model-based prediction approaches. The disadvantages of the model-based approaches are the limitation of modelling interactions and generally shorter prediction horizons compared to data-based approaches. Conversely, data-based approaches can utilize inputs such as previously introduced raster to inform the model of the environment elements influencing the motion of the observed traffic participant. However, the data-based approaches are regarded as black-boxes, with the relationship between input and output inherently unexplainable. To leverage the advantages and address the disadvantages of both classes of approaches, a hybrid model has been proposed that combines them at the input-output level. This hybrid model incorporates complex inputs, such as raster, through the data-based component while constraining the output according to established physical laws using the model-based approach. This model structure can still allow end-to-end training while enhancing the overall explainability of the prediction model.

Finally, it is worth noting that the initial version of the motion prediction model was previously reported on in deliverable D3.1 through a model card example. The readers were provided with the design and development information available prior to the submission of the deliverable. Updates on the model's development stage will be incorporated into the presented model card, with new model cards generated as future versions of the model undergo development and testing. Since the model card includes a section dedicated to the evaluation of the model's

performance, the D5.2 and D5.3 can be coupled with the model card currently provided as part of the D3.1 and future versions of the model card shared through the project's website.

Results of the evaluation from the 1st cycle (VIF)

Currently, the sub-components of the LDM and the intermediate input generator have been successfully implemented and are used to generate training and testing data from the selected datasets. However, to analyse the model's performance comprehensively, an additional parameter has been introduced to the intermediate input generation process. With the ontology recognizing a set of environment elements that can interact with the observed traffic participant, the intermediate input generation can now be customized to output raster encoding only a certain class of elements. Moreover, the additional parameter enabled the specification of the class of traffic participants that will be the primary focus for motion prediction.

With a more flexible generation of the intermediate inputs, the training and the testing of the prediction model can be performed incrementally. These stages are delineated based on the classes influencing the motion of the target traffic participant, with the initial stages focusing on the isolated effects of individual classes of environment elements. Therefore, the ongoing training of the model will reveal the impact road infrastructure has on the pedestrians' motion. Particular emphasis will be placed on scenarios involving pedestrians crossing at intersections.

Outlook for the 2nd cycle (VIF)

Having generated the training and testing datasets and finalized the model methodology, the second cycle will initially prioritize iterative evaluation of KPI_04 and KPI_05. Each iteration will align with the development stages outlined in the Setup section, offering a comprehensive understanding of how each class of environment element influences each class of traffic participants. These iterations will also involve identifying special cases that may present additional challenges for motion prediction.

Given that the datasets used for intermediate input generation encompass only a subset of scenarios and, consequently, element observations anticipated of the urban environment, the developmental focus will shift towards diversifying training and testing scenarios. The aim is to leverage the outcomes of perception components developed as part of UC2.2, potentially enriching scenarios with observations of transient elements such as changing traffic lights or vehicle signal lights, as well as static elements such as free space detection, to further detail the map information. Expanding the scenarios dataset will be followed by additional iterations of KPI evaluation, facilitating an even more robust assessment.

5. UC3 – Trustworthy and Human understandable Decision-making

As already described in “D5.1 Testing and evaluation methodology for AI-driven CCAM systems” UC 3 relates to the task of the guidance of automated vehicles. Since the models and algorithms for vehicle guidance are responsible for the generation of driving manoeuvres and thus need to make reasonable decisions, they have a direct impact on how people in and outside the vehicle perceive this behaviour. This has implications on how people think about automated vehicles in general, and on various aspects such as safety, comfort, efficiency, and many others.

Overall, it can be concluded that the algorithms for vehicle guidance have a significant impact on the trustworthiness of automated vehicles. The understandability of such algorithms and the decision-making process can therefore increase trust in automated vehicles in general.

The UC therefore focuses on two different aspects:

The first aspect is to implement a system that is robust enough to handle as much situations as possible in an understandable way. To this end, all available information (onboard perception, map-data, external communication...) for the decision-making process should be combined and considered, and secondly, a method for monitoring the competence of data-driven approaches for vehicle guidance should be implemented. By estimating the competence of algorithms in specific situations, the robustness of the overall system can then be further increased.

Secondly, an interface should be provided to display the essential information that led to specific decisions for the occupants of automated vehicles. It should be possible to explain decisions to the occupants via this interface. It should be noted here that the focus is not on the ideal implementation of the human-machine interface, but on providing an information interface to the algorithms for automated vehicle guidance. This should be illustrated through a rudimentary visualisation of these information.

The following sections describe the evaluation of the initial developments during the 1st cycle of the project and present first results. Section 5.1 describes the simulation setup used for the evaluation and the integration of the developed algorithms into this simulation framework. Section 5.2 will then discuss the results of the simulative evaluation, while 5.3 will give a brief outlook on the second cycle of the project.

5.1. Setup

The task of automated vehicle guidance can be interpreted as a control loop: The vehicle finds itself in a defined state within its environment. The state of the vehicle as well as that of all surrounding traffic participants is perceived by a variety of sensors for environmental perception. The perception modules interpret the sensor data and use it to model the vehicle's surroundings. Additional information such as map data or information received via external communication can be used to enrich the modelling. This so-called environment model can then be used to derive decisions about the driving behaviour and generate corresponding vehicle trajectories. The control loop is finally closed through the modules for control and actuation, as the vehicle is moved, which changes its own state. Next to this, also the state of the surrounding traffic participants may change, which is perceived by the sensors, leading to an updated version of the environment model enabling the next iteration of the decision making and trajectory planning process.

The description of this control loop emphasises the fact, that for a representative testing and evaluation of algorithms for vehicle guidance of automated vehicles, this control loop must be closed. For simulative testing, this requires the feedback of the generated manipulated variables in order to place the vehicle in the simulated environment according to the planned movement. This represents a significant difference, for example, to the testing of algorithms for vehicle perception, which can be evaluated offline using recorded sensor data, for example.

For the evaluation of UC 3, the open-source simulator *CARLA* [18] is used. As ika’s automated driving software stack is based on a microservice architecture, the open-source framework *CARLOS*¹ [19] which is also developed by ika is used more specifically. *CARLOS* provides a containerized simulation framework enabling different use cases like software prototyping, data-driven development, and scalable automated testing.

Various *ROS* [20] applications were integrated as microservices into the simulation framework using *docker-ros*² [21]. In addition to the actual software modules for automated vehicle guidance, the open-source *ROS* package stack *etsi_its_messages*³ was also developed and integrated into the simulation framework. This allows the integration of standardised *ETSI ITS* message definitions⁴ into the *ROS* ecosystem [22], contributing significantly to the fulfilment of the requirement REQ_28 from D5.1. The resulting architecture of the simulation framework in combination with the developed and integrated applications is illustrated in Figure 44.

Figure 44: UC3 Microservice Simulation Architecture

Figure 44 shows the integration of the functional architecture proposed in D5.1 into the microservice simulation framework. The software modules on the application layer are more specifically *ROS 2* executables that communicate through the *ROS 2* middleware. To integrate these *ROS 2* executables into the microservice architecture, a specific *docker* image for each

¹ <https://github.com/ika-rwth-aachen/carlos>

² <https://github.com/ika-rwth-aachen/docker-ros>

³ https://github.com/ika-rwth-aachen/etsi_its_messages

⁴ <https://forge.etsi.org/rep/ITS/asn1>

executable is generated using *docker-ros*. This enables the evaluation of the UC scenarios to be executed and evaluated in a reproducible, scalable and, if necessary, automated manner.

Referring to the proposed scenarios, it is intended to perform the simulative evaluation using a digital twin of the test track where the physical testing will be performed. Therefore, the *Aldenhoven Testing Center*⁵ has been modelled and integrated into the simulation environment (cf. Figure 45).

Figure 45: Aldenhoven Testing Center modelled in CARLA

5.2. Results of the evaluation in the 1st cycle

The following paragraphs will describe the evaluation results for UC3 based on the works of the first cycle. While section 5.2.1 describes the results for the Hybrid AI Motion Planning stack, developed by ika, the results on TNO's competence observation are presented in 5.2.2.

5.2.1. Evaluation of Hybrid AI Motion Planning Stack

Since design and development of the Hybrid AI Planning stack, the definition of the use-case scenarios along with the specific evaluation metrics as well as the modelling of the simulation environment, have been tackled in parallel, it wasn't possible to evaluate the initial prototype function yet in the defined scenarios and by using the specific KPIs defined in D5.1.

Nevertheless, evaluations have been performed for the CNN based behaviour generation in a separate manner, as well as a full prototype of the motion planning stack, composed of CNN based behaviour generation and the subsequent trajectory supervision module.

For evaluation of the composed stack and more specific the trajectory supervision module a CNN model was utilized that uses a birds-eye-view image as input (three channels representing the ego vehicle, map information and other vehicles in the local vehicle environment) to predict a vehicle trajectory with four states t , x , y , and v representing the time, the x- and y-position of the vehicle

⁵ <https://www.aldenhoven-testing-center.de/en/>

and the velocity to be reached at the specific point. The utilized Network architecture is based on the EfficientNetB0 [23]. It should be noted at this point that there was no focus on the chosen network architecture, nor on the choice of input and label representation, as the network is primarily used to develop and evaluate the trajectory supervision. Figure 46 shows the pipeline utilized for Training of the CNN: Input and label information were derived from CARLA [18] simulations, leading to an imitation of the behaviour of the CARLA driver.

Figure 46: Training pipeline for CNN based behaviour generation utilized to evaluate the trajectory supervision

As illustrated in Figure 44, the output trajectory of the CNN is fed into the trajectory supervision module that should ensure for a drivability of the trajectory, as well as checking rudimentary checking rules like validating input data, checking for potential collisions, ensuring a sufficient optimization horizon or avoiding leaving the road boundaries. If one of the rule-check fails, the trajectory is modified in a way, that the vehicle is still able to continue its drive. If the modifications are not sufficient to ensure a safe behaviour, a fail-safe manoeuvre is initiated.

The evaluation of the trajectory supervision module is performed through two scenarios using one of the sample towns shipped with CARLA. Throughout the first scenario, the vehicle is intended to perform a left turn under disturbance of three different vehicles. The other scenario starts on the same intersection, but in this case the vehicle should perform a right turn, followed by another right and left turn leading to the route as proposed in Figure 47. The behaviour of the vehicle challenging the ego vehicle is specifically defined to achieve deterministic simulation scenarios.

Figure 47: Scenarios utilized for evaluation of the trajectory supervision.

During simulation of each scenario, we recorded the trajectory predicted by the CNN, the trajectory that may have been modified through the trajectory supervision as well as the driven trajectory of the vehicle. Figure 48 visualizes the different trajectories on a 2D plane, allowing for a qualitative evaluation of the capabilities of the trajectory supervision. By inspecting the red trajectory sets (supervisor output) and comparing them with the grey ones (CNN output), it becomes clear that the trajectories predicted by the CNN are significantly changed by the supervisor and scatter within the CNN trajectories is reduced. While the vehicle is able to execute both scenarios, the actual resulting trajectory still significantly differs from the output trajectories of the supervisor. Looking at the trajectory driven in more general terms, it becomes noticeable that the vehicle is not able to follow the planned trajectory properly, especially while turning: The actual trajectory somehow deviates in direction of the outer side of the route along a curve, which resembles understeering behaviour.

Figure 48: 2D Plot of the different trajectories recorded in both simulation scenarios allowing a qualitative evaluation of the capabilities of the trajectory supervision module

In addition to the qualitative analysis, the x-y deviation of the individual trajectories from each other was also evaluated quantitatively, which supports the subjective findings. Overall, it can be stated here that the proposed architecture for motion planning tends to be capable of guiding the vehicle according to the planned route, but the resulting driving behaviour does not represent the actual desired behaviour. In particular, the deviation of the trajectory that was actually driven with respect to the trajectory suggested by the supervisor should be investigated further. This is not necessarily due to a lack of drivability of the planned trajectory, but due to an insufficient vehicle stabilisation along the planned route. These problems shall be addressed in the second cycle of the project, as referred to in section 5.3.1.

It should be noted at this point that the experiments presented here did not focus on good performance of the predicted CNN trajectory. Rather, the basic concepts of the supervision and the resulting architecture for motion planning should be validated here. In addition to some weaknesses in the trajectory supervision, which will be worked on in the further course of the project, in Figure 48 it can be observed that some of the trajectories predicted by the CNN are located on the pavement. The main reason for this is a small training data set and the simple network architecture utilized for this evaluation. To counteract this, different network architectures for trajectory prediction were examined in parallel, the initial findings of which are described in the following paragraph:

We investigated The performance of different network architectures for supervised learning-based behaviour generation has been investigated. Compared to the CNN presented above (cf. Figure 46), the input representation for the improved neural network was also adapted accordingly. Please refer to D3.2 for further information on this. To summarise, both CNN and Vision-Transformer (ViT) architectures have been trained and evaluated. For training and

validation, the nuPlan6 [24] dataset was used. The evaluated CNN architectures all based on the VGG16 [25], [26]. For the ViTs three different characteristics have been evaluated based on the works of Dosovitskiy et. Al. [27] and Carion et. Al. [28]. In addition, variations with different parameterisations (e.g. different parameterisations of the individual layers, dropout rates or different patch sizes in the case of ViTs) were also examined in relation to the four different basic architectures. In summary, it was found that a CNN-based architecture provides the best overall performance for the approach shown here, utilizing the corresponding in- and output representation while also showing shorter inference times.

5.2.2. Evaluation of Competence Observation

The competence observation method developed by TNO is based on the notion that competence is related to experience. Situations and environments that have been encountered more frequently and in greater variety can be handled with more competence than their unfamiliar counterparts.

Finding out the similarity between two different road contexts is key to showing that similar contexts have been trained on by the trajectory-generating model. The first results show that the approach of calculating the similarity in road context on a relational and symbolic level is possible.

In the following experiment, it is shown that the similarity algorithm described in D3.2 for comparing graph representations of the road layout is able to give higher scores to similar contexts compared to other contexts. It is shown that contexts close to the same infrastructural elements have a higher similarity score. This was done by selecting four locations from the NuPlan [24] training data as samples. These samples are taken from the Boston location and hand-picked near a roundabout, a four-way intersection, a straight road, and a three-way intersection. Besides this, three locations from the Las Vegas map of the NuPlan data were selected and compared in context similarity to the four samples in Boston using the similarity measure.

Table 7 shows the different samples for each infrastructure type in Boston. Table 8 shows the different infrastructure examples for Las Vegas. These two tables have the following content. First, a Google Maps visual of the location is given. Secondly, the map data from NuPlan is visualized where the road elements that are considered to be in the context are highlighted in yellow (lanes) and orange (connectors). These are road elements that are within 50 meters of the ego and are in any way connected to the lane the ego vehicle is on. Excluded road segments are shown in blue. Finally, the graph representation is shown, which is automatically generated from the map data and the ego position. In this representation, pink nodes are lanes, yellow nodes are lane markings, blue nodes are connectors and green nodes are pedestrian crossings. For example, in the Boston straight road sample, the graph shows the lane the ego vehicle is currently on and the lane next to that lane. These lanes are connected by a lane marking. Additionally, each lane has another lane marking on the other side of the lane.

Table 7: Boston road context samples.

Boston Samples	Three-way intersection	Four-way intersection	Roundabout	Straight Road

⁶ <https://www.nuscenes.org/nuplan>

Visual of road				
Map visualization				
Graph representation				

Table 8: Las Vegas road context samples.

Las Vegas Samples	Three-way intersection	Roundabout	Straight Road
Visual of road			
Map visualization			
Graph representation			

The graph similarity measure is based on an iterative application of a graph editing distance measure [29] with custom weight on subgraphs of the context graph. The graph is iteratively expanded, starting at the lane node that the ego vehicle is currently driving on and stopping when it either cannot expand anymore or when the computed similarity measure drops below a certain

threshold. By doing so, similarities for the close neighbourhood of the ego vehicle can be extracted, while also considering the road network at large. A more comprehensive explanation of the algorithm can be found in D3.2.

The results of the similarity measure are shown in Table 9. The presented similarity scores are the mean similarities over the subgraphs from three up to ten nodes away from the ego lane node. From the similarity measure, it can be seen that contexts of the same infrastructure type achieve the highest similarity scores. This is as expected. It can be observed that the roundabout structure achieves the lowest similarity score across. This can be explained by the fact that the roundabout on the Las Vegas map is quite different, as it has many more lanes and fewer exists compared to the roundabout on the Boston map.

Table 9: The similarities between the Las Vegas samples and the Boston samples. In the last column the competence scores are stated, given the model has observed only the four Boston samples as its Dataset.

Boston Las Vegas	Roundabout	Three-way Intersection	Four-way Intersection	Straight Road	Competence score
Straight Road	0.226	0.381	0.260	0.643	0.531
Roundabout	0.511	0.475	0.465	0.136	0.580
Three-way Intersection	0.472	0.564	0.489	0.226	0.591

Finally, the competence for each infrastructure type can be computed as the weighted average over all similarity scores, with scores computed for smaller subgraphs (i.e. the graphs including map elements that are close to the ego) receiving larger weights than the larger subgraphs (i.e. the graphs including map elements that are further away).

Good to note is that the competence scores calculated in the experiment are not based on the whole train dataset of NuPlan but they only show the competence in the Las Vegas contexts based on the four examples from Boston as the dataset. As this is not a representable sample of the whole dataset, the resulting competence scores are not a good representation of the real scores based on the whole NuPlan Dataset. However, it shows that the competence is higher for the contexts which have more similar samples in the dataset.

5.3. Outlook for the 2nd cycle

The following paragraphs propose an outlook for the second cycle of Athena regarding UC3.

5.3.1. Outlook for Hybrid AI Motion Planning

As shown in section 5.2.1, the approaches for hybrid-ai motion planning still show significant potential for improvement. The data-driven behaviour planning shall be continuously developed, with a focus on training using additional training data (e.g. the inD dataset [30]), possibly also for specific scenarios (e.g. junctions or roundabouts).

Regarding the rule-based trajectory supervision, it became apparent that additional logic needs to be implemented. One possible solution would be the integration of a non-linear Model-Predictive-Controller (MPC) for the optimisation of the trajectory using a vehicle model and by considering several constraints and costs.

The approaches should be further tested and evaluated using the proposed simulation architecture. In addition, the scenarios presented in D5.1 are also to be integrated and the defined KPIs should be analysed.

One main goal of the second cycle will be the integration of the developed software modules into a real-world demonstrator. In this case the real-world demonstrator will be ika's research vehicle, allowing closed loop testing of the implemented algorithms. In addition to the further development of the presented algorithms, the interface for visualizing relevant information to vehicle occupants, should be implemented more intensively.

5.3.2. Outlook for Competence Observation

The modelling of the road context for the similarity and competence measure will be further developed. For example, in the current translation to the graph, the lane length is not taken into account. As a next step this will be addressed by splitting lanes into parts of equal length. Also, not only the road infrastructure has an influence on the planner competence. By adding the dynamic road context to the graph e.g. road users, the relevance of the competence measure will be increased.

In the current results, the similarity has been calculated between four infrastructure samples from Boston and three samples from Las Vegas from the NuPlan dataset. It is important to keep in mind that this has been done as a proof of concept. The actual competence of the planner will be calculated by comparing the road context the ego vehicle is in, to all the road contexts encountered before in the training dataset. To do this, the computational performance of the similarity measure has to be increased.

The main goal of the second cycle will be to improve the speed and accuracy of the competence measure and to evaluate the measure on the KPIs defined in D5.1 against a trajectory generation model trained on the NuPlan dataset. Besides that, integration with the ika's setup interfaces is a priority, such that the competence evaluation of the trajectory generation planner can be evaluated in the predefined use-cases from D5.1.

6. UC4 – AI-based Traffic management

This use case “AI-based Traffic Management (TM)” focuses on the impact of AI-based Automated Vehicles (AVs) on the network level from a traffic management perspective.

UC4 AI-based TM predominantly takes a virtual approach for the two cycles of the Althena project to assess the interactions of AVs and non-AVs under different vehicle compositions using microsimulation (modelling of movement and behaviour of individual vehicle such as speed, car following, lane changing, trajectory, decision making, interaction of AVs and non-AVs, etc.). Using microsimulation, the impact of how introducing AVs into a traffic network influencing overall traffic dynamics, can be studied on the network level from a traffic management perspective. The evaluation focuses on efficiency in the first cycle and on efficiency, safety, and sustainability in the second cycle. By studying the results of the simulations, the behaviours of AI-based AVs become more explainable and the impact of introducing of AVs in the network becomes more transparent and by extension it increases trustworthiness of the AI-based AVs for primarily traffic managers.

D5.1 states the high-level requirements, validation approach, testing and evaluation overview of UC4 AI-based Traffic management (TM). In this deliverable, the results retrieved from using the aforementioned testing and evaluation approach are shown and discussed.

6.1. Setup

6.1.1. UC4 proof-of-concept—first cycle

In the first cycle of Althena, UC4 has developed a proof-of-concept (PoC) design and realised it via a virtual approach using microscopic simulation (see D3.2 UC4 design). This small-scale demonstrator network is set up using VISSIM to fulfil the high-level requirements of UC4. A timeline and corresponding algorithm have been created for a vehicle breakdown scenario including AVs and non-AVs to analyse the network level effect of their behaviours. The proof-of-concept focuses on the first order effect of UC4, avoiding unknown cascading effects to a higher order in larger, more complicated networks.

The incident in the PoC network blocks a single lane-urban road, which is separated by a solid line from the opposite lane (see Figure 49). This is a particularly challenging situation for AVs since common sense logic of a competent driver allows for overtaking the incident by crossing the solid line but the traffic rules strictly do not.

Figure 49: UC4 proof-of-concept schematic layout.

The behaviour of the non-AVs is defined as the desired behaviour and forms the benchmark/baseline. The non-AVs following the breakdown vehicle, perceive the incident and sequentially overtake it by crossing the solid line using the opposite lane taking oncoming traffic into account. The AVs following the incident might not have been developed with the desired logic to ignore the “Rule Of The Road” (ROTR), cross the solid line and overtake the breakdown vehicle.

When the breakdown incident occurs, the incident is perceived by the Road Side Infrastructure (RSI) at once. From that moment, the traffic management (TM) control measure of using the

opposite lane to overtake the breakdown incident and stopping for oncoming traffic, is being broadcast via TM V2X messages. All vehicles subscribe to the TM message, receive, and decrypt the V2X message. Using those messages, AVs trusting that information, overtake the incident without hesitation while AVs not trusting the information do so only after a backup system kicks in (i.e., handover, remote control/guidance after a certain delay). This is the key component of the PoC. The AV behaviour in UC4 is dependent on the TM information and the AV's trust towards that information. If the TM information is available and the AV trusts the TM information, the 'AV-with-trust' vehicle type can overcome the situation. If not, the 'AV-without trust' vehicle type stops for 10 seconds until the backup system enables the AV to overtake the incident.

Using the proof-of-concept network, configured vehicle logics and vehicle compositions (see D3.2), UC4 evaluates the macroscopic network level impact of the AV penetration rates and AV trust levels towards the TM information in heterogenous traffic.

In the context of UC4 PoC, two hypotheses are proposed regarding the UC4 PoC outcomes when the Level Of Service (LOS) on a network is fixed:

H₁ — When the percentage of AV-with-trust is fixed at an arbitrary value, the higher the percentage of AVs among all vehicles, the higher the total vehicle delay is.

H₂ — When the percentage of AVs is fixed at an arbitrary value, the higher the percentage of AV-with-trust, the lower the total vehicle delay is.

6.1.2. UC4 proof-of-concept network setup in VISSIM

This section sets up the UC4 PoC network in VISSIM simulation tool. Table 10 lists the configurations and geometrical characteristics of the UC4 PoC network in VISSIM.

Table 10: UC4 PoC network overview in VISSIM configuration

UC4 PoC in VISSIM	Settings	Notes
Road section length	390 m	
Behaviour type	Urban	
Allowed road speed	13.89 m/s	50±2 km/h
Number of connectors	2	
Number of links	4	
Number of O-D relations	2	
Number of lanes	1 or 2	
Breakdown incident location	Link3_lane1	Position 154 m from start of Link3_lane1
Link with overtaking lane	Link3_lane2	
Filenames	incident av.inpx	
<p><i>Traffic management control of incident</i> The RSI detects the incident and provides (broadcasts) TM messages to all vehicles on the network. The exclusive westbound directional lane usage (pink dashed lane section) is open to the following vehicles (indicated by yellow box). The following vehicles includes non-AVs, AV-with-trust and AV-without-trust (after stopping behind the breakdown vehicle for 10 seconds).</p>		
<p><i>Network layout</i></p>		
<p><i>Overtaking snapshot</i></p>		

6.2. Results of the evaluation in the first cycle

D3.2 reports on building of the initial AV composition matrix. The two varying dimensions (with 25% interval): percentage of AV among all vehicles and percentage of AV-with-trust among AVs, generates 25 vehicle mixes for the sensitivity analysis. To capture the stochasticity of the UC4 PoC, each vehicle mix is run 10 times and each time with a different seed number. The 10 seed numbers are fixed across all 25 vehicle mixes for comparison of the two varying dimensions while minimising the cascading effect of randomness.

Following the testing and evaluation methodology in D5.1, the sensitivity analysis is performed with retrieving the targeted KPI — total vehicle delay of the abovementioned 250 simulations on network level. The results of the total vehicle delay correspond to the raised hypotheses in section 6.1.1. It also showed a non-linear result on each varying dimension through the sensitivity analysis experiment. Therefore, a smaller interval of 5% was fitted to the vehicle composition matrix between 0% and 25% and to the level of trust between 75% and 100%.

Table 11 shows the total vehicle delay of the full vehicle composition matrix — 81 mixes, based on 9 percentages of AV (0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 100%) and 9 percentages AV-with-trust (0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 80%, 85%, 90%, 95%, 100%) with respect to the total number of AVs. Similar to the sensitivity analysis, each vehicle mix is run 10 times and each time with a different seed number. The 10 seed numbers are fixed across all 81 vehicle mixes. Thus, the 810 simulations were conducted, and the results were obtained. Next, the results were analysed and visually shown in the coloured Table 11.

Table 11: UC4 Proof-of-concept results of the KPI — Total vehicle delay

Total vehicle delay (hour)	% AV-with-trust								
	0	25	50	75	80	85	90	95	100
0	0.057	0.057	0.057	0.057	0.057	0.057	0.057	0.057	0.057
5	0.141	0.082	0.081	0.084	0.090	0.097	0.102	0.094	0.075
10	0.143	0.135	0.115	0.119	0.104	0.103	0.104	0.088	0.074
15	0.226	0.188	0.155	0.116	0.157	0.099	0.093	0.067	0.113
20	0.200	0.211	0.178	0.158	0.165	0.115	0.099	0.074	0.128
25	0.220	0.193	0.192	0.141	0.165	0.163	0.099	0.098	0.086
50	0.262	0.237	0.219	0.194	0.179	0.162	0.157	0.086	0.076
75	0.239	0.237	0.242	0.202	0.199	0.194	0.120	0.129	0.095
100	0.288	0.273	0.232	0.212	0.187	0.201	0.179	0.117	0.049

The colour scheme with colour gradients (red indicating a relatively high total delay in the network and green a lower delay) in Table 11 shows similar expectations raised by H1 and H2. The baseline for the reference behaviour includes only non-AV vehicles is depicted on the first row. In the reference situation the total vehicle delay in the network is 0.057 hours. The first column (AV-with-trust is 0%) shows that as the percentage of AV-without-trust increases, the network delay also increases. Contrary, when the % of AV-with-trust increases from left to right, the network delay decreases. When the % of AVs is above 5%, only with 95% or 100% trust the performance approaches the baseline performance. Other than these general trends, there are some outliers which can be contributed to stochastic coincidences.

6.3. Outlook for the 2nd cycle

After the successful PoC, we have scanned through possible macroscopic networks for the second cycle demonstrator. Part of the Heemstede city network in the Netherlands fulfilled our high-level requirements and criteria. In the second cycle of Althena, the proof-of-concept network can be upscaled to one intersection and then to the Heemstede network by taking into consideration the UC4 functionalities and results of first cycle.

Figure 50 shows an example of the second cycle UC4 demonstrator. Three consecutive intersections: A, B and C are built to simulation layout, which replicate a part of the geographic network in Heemstede. Real-world datasets from road operator databases such as live traffic systems data and non-AV data, are prepared and configured in the simulation. Calibration of the network will be performed in the second cycle.

This will make it possible to further analyse the propagational network effects of non-AVs, AV-with-trust and AV-without-trust behaviours in corner/edge cases. Other next steps to be considered for UC4 are:

- In addition to upscaling the network, it can be experimented on adding more incidents (i.e.) throughout the network.
- To have a wider overview of the network effect, different LOS levels can be introduced to study the impact of AVs and trust when traffic is less or busier.
- Other KPIs can be added: more metrics of efficiency (MOE) or KPIs for safety and sustainability.
- Regarding simulating AV behaviours, “AV all knowing” instead of “AV cautious” can be used to identify the impact of AV behaviour, where the AV behaviour is more in line with future expectations.
- Combinations of the above.

Figure 50: Simulation layout (left) and geographic (right) network overview of 2nd cycle UC4 — Part of Heemstede

CONCLUSION

This deliverable is the second in WP5 and describes the initial use case evaluation for the first cycle of the project. As the use cases are composed of the work of different partners, it was not yet possible to evaluate joint results at this stage. This report therefore concentrates on evaluating the results of the individual partners, while an evaluation of the joint work within the use cases is planned for the next deliverable (D5.3) at the end of the second cycle.

This document is structured according to the use cases. In UC1 the development of reliable perception systems for connected and automated mobility (CCAM) is discussed. Currently an offline demonstrator based on recorded data, simulated data, and public datasets to prototype, test, and evaluate AI detection functions, particularly for pedestrian detection in urban scenarios is used. This chapter introduces explainable AI methods like saliency map generation to understand AI model behaviour and robust multi-modal pedestrian detection to ensure the reliability of autonomous vehicles under various conditions. Also, the importance of uncertainty quantification in perception systems is explained, allowing autonomous vehicles to make informed decisions. A method called Last Layer Monte-Carlo-Dropout (LLMCD) is proposed for real-time uncertainty estimation in detector models.

Chapter 2 is about the use case 2.1, the first of two demonstrators in use case 2. In the first cycle of the project, the use case focused on developing the semantic labelling pipeline using the nuScenes dataset. The GraphDB data model was used to explore the data model and relationships within the taxonomy. SPARQL queries were executed to identify specific situations in the dataset. These queries broke down high-level semantics into logical triplets, leading to the identification of specific maneuvers. The extracted scenarios allowed for dataset visualization and investigation, providing preliminary insights for future refinement and exploration. This process is crucial for improving autonomous driving systems by identifying weaknesses and aiding in re-training machine learning models.

In chapter 3 the evaluation of the initial results of the second demonstrator of use case two is described. This part describes the AI-enhanced situation awareness for robust prediction modules in urban traffic environments, focusing on the safety and efficiency of Robo-taxis. It highlights the evaluation of topics like Lane detection, traffic light colour / vehicle signal detection comparing different approaches (e.g. different YOLO architectures) for object detection. Also, the effectiveness of the time-triggered runtime in ensuring predictable timing and temporal isolation, which are critical for the safe operation of Robo-taxis is demonstrated.

Use case 3 is covered in chapter 4. It focuses on implementing a system robust enough to handle various situations in an understandable manner. It suggests combining all available information for decision-making and implementing a method to monitor the competence of data-driven approaches for vehicle guidance. An interface should be provided to display essential information that led to specific decisions for the occupants of automated vehicles. This interface aims to explain decisions to the occupants, focusing on the information interface to the algorithms rather than the ideal human-machine interface implementation.

The final chapter describes the evaluation of the first results of UC4. A proof-of-concept scenario was developed with a vehicle breakdown incident on a two-lane road with opposite directions separated by a solid line. When the AI of AVs is unable to overcome the incident without traffic management (TM) information, the network level efficiency significantly decreases when the percentage of AVs among all vehicles increases. Providing TM information on how to overcome

the situation could help the AI to overcome the incident but it needs to be able to process and trust the information. When using the TM information to overcome the incident, the network level efficiency increases when the percentage of AVs using the TM Information increases.

Bibliography

- [1] T. Beemelmans, W. Zahr and L. Eckstein, *Explainable Multi-Camera 3D Object Detection with Transformer-Based Saliency Maps*, 2023.
- [2] S. Doll, R. Schulz, L. Schneider, V. Benzin, E. Markus and H. P. Lensch, "SpatialDETR: Robust Scalable Transformer-Based 3D Object Detection from Multi-View Camera Images with Global Cross-Sensor Attention," in *European Conference on Computer Vision(ECCV)*, 2022.
- [3] T. B. a. Q. Z. a. L. Eckstein, *MultiCorrupt: A Multi-Modal Robustness Dataset and Benchmark of LiDAR-Camera Fusion for 3D Object Detection*, 2024.
- [4] J. Yan, Y. Liu, J. Sun, F. Jia, S. Li, T. Wang and X. Zhang, *Cross Modal Transformer via Coordinates Encoding for 3D Object Detection*, 2023.
- [5] Y. Wang, A. Fathi, A. Kundu, D. Ross, C. Pantofaru, T. Funkhouser and J. Solomon, *Pillar-based Object Detection for Autonomous Driving*, 2020.
- [6] A. Radford, J. W. Kim, C. a. R. A. a. G. G. Hallacy, S. Agarwal, G. Sastry, A. Askell, P. Mishkin and J. Clark, "Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision," in *International conference on machine learning*, PMLR, 2021, pp. 8748-8763.
- [7] J. Stallkamp, M. Schlipsing, J. Salmen and C. Igel, "The German traffic sign recognition benchmark: a multi-class classification competition," in *The 2011 international joint conference on neural networks*, IEEE, 2011, pp. 1453-1460.
- [8] M. Alibeigi, W. Ljungbergh, A. Tonderski, G. Hess, A. Lilja, C. Lindstrom, D. Motorniuk, J. Fu, J. Widahl and C. Petersson, "Zenseact Open Dataset: A large-scale and diverse multimodal dataset for autonomous driving," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2023, pp. 20178-20188.
- [9] G. Neuhold, T. Ollmann, S. Rota Bulò and P. Kotschieder, "The mapillary vistas dataset for semantic understanding of street scenes," in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, 2017, pp. 4990-4999.
- [10] K. L. Hobbs, M. L. Mote, M. C. L. Abate, S. D. Coogan and E. M. Feron, "Runtime Assurance for Safety-Critical Systems: An Introduction to Safety Filtering Approaches for Complex Control Systems," *IEEE Control Systems Magazine*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. pp. 28-65, April 2023.
- [11] A. Pandharipande and e. al., "Sensing and Machine Learning for Automotive Perception: A Review," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. pp. 11097 - 11115, June 2023.
- [12] "Simcenter Prescan Software simulation platform. [Online]," [Online]. Available: <https://plm.sw.siemens.com/en-US/simcenter/autonomous-vehicle-solutions/prescan/>.
- [13] J. Redmon and A. Farhadi, "YOLOv3: An Incremental Improvement," arXiv, 2018.
- [14] A. Forrai and H. Hotait, "Digital twin for synthetic data generation - application for automated driving systems," in *DSC 2023 Europe VR 22nd Driving Simulation and Virtual Reality Conference*, Antibes, France, 2023.
- [15] A. Forrai, V. Neelgundmath, K. Unni and I. Barosan, "Runtime Safety Assurance of Autonomous Vehicles," *2023 7th International Conference on System Reliability and Safety (ICSRS)*, pp. 290-299, 2023.
- [16] R. R. Selvaraju, A. Das, R. Vedantam, M. Cogswell, D. Parikh and D. Batra, *Grad-cam: Why did you say that? visual explanations from deep networks via gradient-based localization*, 2016.

- [17] P. Karachatzis, J. Ruh and S. Craciunas, "An Evaluation of Time-triggered Scheduling in the Linux Kernel," *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Real-Time Networks and Systems*, 2023.
- [18] A. Dosovitskiy, G. Ros, F. Codevilla, A. Lopez and V. Koltun, "CARLA: An open urban driving simulator," in *Proceedings of the 1st Annual Conference on Robot Learning*, 2017.
- [19] C. Geller, B. Haas, A. Kloeker, J. Hermens, B. Lampe and L. Eckstein, "CARLOS - An Open, Modular, and Scalable Simulation Framework for the Development and Testing of Software for C-ITS," arXiv, 2024.
- [20] S. Macenski, T. Foote, B. Gerkey, C. Lalancette and W. Woodall, "Robot Operating System 2: Design, architecture, and uses in the wild," *Science Robotics*, vol. 7, no. 66, 2022.
- [21] J.-P. Busch, L. Reiher and L. Eckstein, "Enabling the Deployment of Any-Scale Robotic Applications in Microservice Architectures through Automated Containerization," arXiv, 2023.
- [22] G. Kueppers, J.-P. Busch, L. Reiher and L. Eckstein, "V2AIX: A Multi-Modal Real-World Dataset of ETSI ITS V2X Messages in Public Road Traffic," arXiv, 2024.
- [23] M. Tan and Q. Le, "Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks," in *International conference on machine learning*, 2019.
- [24] H. Caesar, J. Kabzan, K. S. Tan, W. K. Fong, E. Wolf, A. Lang, L. Fletcher, O. Beijbom and S. Omari, "NuPlan: A closed-loop ML-based planning benchmark for autonomous vehicles," in *CVPR ADP3 Workshop*, 2021.
- [25] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman, "Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition," in *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2015.
- [26] H. u. Muneeb, "VGG16 - Convolutional Network for Classification and Detection," 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://neurohive.io/en/popular-networks/vgg16/>. [Accessed 04 04 2024].
- [27] A. Dosovitskiy, L. Beyer, A. Kolesnikov, D. Weissenborn, X. Zhai, T. Unterthiner, M. Dehghani, M. Minderer, G. Heigold and S. Gelly, "An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale," arXiv, 2020.
- [28] N. Carion, F. Massa, G. Synnaeve, N. Usunier, A. Kirillov and S. Zagoruyko, "End-to-end object detection with transformers," in *European conference on computer vision*, 2020.
- [29] Z. Abu-Aisheh, R. Raveaux, J.-Y. Ramel and P. Martineau, "An Exact Graph Edit Distance Algorithm for Solving Pattern Recognition Problems," in *4th International Conference on Pattern Recognition Applications and Methods*, Lisbon, 2015.
- [30] J. Bock, R. Krajewski, T. Moers, S. Runde, L. Vater and L. Eckstein, "The inD Dataset: A Drone Dataset of Naturalistic Road User Trajectories at German Intersections," in *2020 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, 2020.

